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Rafał Wiktor KOWALCZYK

WHY DID MOSCOW WIN THE COMPETITION FOR DOMINANCE IN THE BLACK SEA REGION? REASONS AND CONSEQUENCES

The destruction of the Great Horde by the Crimean Khan from the Giray dynasty, Mengli I Giray, and the symbolic destruction of the mythical capital of the Great Horde, Sarai Berke, altered the balance of power in the region. A new power structure began to emerge based on the competition for the succession of the last nomadic states of the Mongol Empire. At that time, the Crimean Khanate became a significant player in the Black Sea region.

However, mistakes made by the Crimean Khanate in its struggle against Moscow, and the failed attempt to take control of the independent Volga Khanates that had emerged from the disintegration of the Golden Horde in the 15th century, ultimately influenced the fate of Eastern, and later Central, Europe. The Crimean Khanate was the natural successor of the Golden Horde, which made the Girays both rulers of the Khanate and rivals of the Great Horde. They considered the Great Horde their main competitor. In Sarai, there was a similar belief that the Great Horde was the sole legitimate heir of the Golden Horde.

At that time, the following powers competed for the territories of the Golden Horde: the Crimean Khanate, the Kazan Khanate, the Astrakhan Khanate, the Grand Duchy of Moscow, and the joint state of the Jagiellonians – Poland with Lithuania. The Crimean Khanate regarded the Great Horde as its natural adversary in establishing primacy over the states that had emerged from the disintegration of the Golden Horde. Moscow skillfully exploited the growing systemic conflict between the Crimean Khanate and the Great Horde.

In 1502, Khan Mengli I Giray destroyed the capital of the Great Horde, Sarai Berke, bringing an end to the Great Horde, an action prompted by Moscow. This was a major success for Moscow, which,

through the Crimean Tatars, eliminated one of the threats from the east in the struggle for supremacy over Asia and Eastern Europe following the collapse of the Golden Horde.

The Crimean Khanate also missed the opportunity to take control of the Volga Khanates – Kazan and Astrakhan – and its attempt to restore the khanates conquered by Ivan IV the Terrible of Moscow ended in failure. For the Crimean Khanate, the Kazan Khanate was particularly important. Initially, Kazan was a strong nomadic state; the Kazan Tatars raided the upper Volga valley, penetrated deep into the Grand Duchy of Moscow, and even approached its capital, Moscow.

However, as Moscow grew stronger, the Kazan Khanate weakened. Its weakness stemmed from the fragile state structure: the Kazan Khanate was sparsely populated and lacked robust state institutions. This institutional void became the foundation for its decline when confronted with the well-organized Muscovite state. Moscow began to interfere in the internal affairs of the khanate, bribing supporters, and luring them with promises of future offices and donations.

The Girays had a chance to transform the Crimean Khanate into an empire; however, the *raison d'état* of the state was undermined by its nomadic character. The Crimean Tatars gradually realized that Moscow posed a greater threat than the Jagiellonian state. Only the successes of Vasili III in the war against the Grand Duchy of Lithuania alarmed the Crimean Khanate. Moscow's triumph proved disastrous for the Crimean Khanate, especially as the Grand Duchy of Moscow was the main competitor of Bakhchisarai and rivaled the Girays over the Kazan Khanate.

The weakness of the Jagiellonian state and the rising power of Moscow, which forcibly subjugated the Rus' lands, prompted Bakhchisarai to change its strategy. At that time, a rapprochement occurred between Bakhchisarai and Kraków. In Kraków, they were aware of the state's weakness and of the growing threat from the east posed by Moscow, which was far greater than the threat from the Crimean Khanate. Consequently, agreement was reached to pay the Crimean Khanate gifts in Bakhchisarai, treated as tribute.

As a result, in 1507, Khan Mengli Giray confirmed all the grants of the previous khans and recognized the Grand Duchy of

Lithuania's rights to the Rus' lands formerly belonging to the Golden Horde. However, the Polish-Muscovite war of 1507 did not bring success for the Crimean Khanate. Moscow's diplomacy proved far more effective. Khan Mengli Giray launched a campaign against Moscow, but the Muscovites allied with the Nogai Horde, hostile to the Crimean Khanate, which carried out a diversionary strike on the Crimea.

Vasili III's successes in the war against Lithuania greatly alarmed the Crimean Khanate. The shift toward Moscow had disastrous consequences for the Crimean Khanate, especially since it was the Grand Duchy of Moscow that competed with Bakhchisarai over the Kazan Khanate. The Crimean Tatars very slowly realized that Moscow was becoming the greatest threat to their state and their previous dominance in the region.

Although from 1520 Bakhchisarai was an ally of the Polish state and a series of raiding expeditions were directed against Moscow, devastating the southern territories of the Rurikid state, the Crimean Khanate still failed to take the opportunity to eliminate Moscow – the greatest threat to all the regional states¹.

The Crimean Khanate did not seize the chance to neutralize the threat from Moscow, even though Ivan IV the Terrible feared confrontation with the Crimean Khanate, backed by the power of the Ottoman Empire. Instead of eliminating the threat originating in Moscow, the Crimean Khanate carried out raiding expeditions on the southern borders of the Rurikid state. The reason lay not only in the nomadic character of the Crimean Khanate, in the very structure of the Giray state and its nomadic perception of *raison d'état*, but also in the military weakness of the Polish-Lithuanian state, a potential ally whose warfare methods were outdated. The foundation of Kraków's armed strength was still the archaic noble levy.

¹ L. PODHORODECKI, *Chanat krymski i jego stosunki z Polską w XV–XVIII wieku*, Warszawa, 1987, s. 97–101; P. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Кримський Ханат у боротьбі за володіння Золотої Орди. XV–XVI століття. Поразка Гіреїв у боротьбі з Москвою', *Наш Крим: До 700-ліття проголошення Кафи головною генуезькою колонією в Криму*, ред. кол. Г. ПАПАКІН (голова); за ред. Д. ГОРДІЄНКА та В. КОРНІЄНКА, вип. III (К., 2018): 64–67.

The weakness of the Polish state was closely linked to the evolution of its political and social system. The death of Casimir the Great, which turned the throne of the Kingdom of Poland into an elective one, led to constitutional transformations. From a state organized by estates, Poland transformed into a nobility republic. This process was initiated by Louis I of Hungary, who, seeking to secure the Polish throne for his dynasty, made concessions to the nobility. Subsequently, the political evolution under the Jagiellonians prevented the burghers from establishing a lasting role in public life. This was also influenced by the fact that their position was not regulated by general privileges, as was the case for the nobility. The death of the last ruler from the native Piast dynasty, Casimir the Great, initiated an irreversible process of economic weakening of the peasantry, a marked decline in the status of the townspeople, and the privileging of the nobility².

Louis I of Hungary was determined to secure the throne in Kraków for his dynasty and made significant concessions to the nobility, beginning a process that undermined the state. By creating a privileged nobility, he laid the foundation for the emergence of the “noble nation” and in the long term, this led to the erosion of the political system, the oligarchization of the state, and ultimately the dissolution of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth in 1795. The origins of this process can be traced back to the Angevin period. In 1374, in Košice, Louis I granted the nobility their first privileges in exchange for recognizing his daughter, Jadwiga, as his successor. Similarly, Władysław Jagiełło sought support for his sons’ claims to the throne (Władysław and Casimir). The privileges granted by Louis I and Jagiełło laid the groundwork for subsequent noble rights, which transformed the nobility into the only estate with political rights and legal-economic superiority over the burgher and peasant estates in the Kingdom of Poland, which was evolving into a nobility republic.

² R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Czy to Jagiellonowie doprowadzili do upadku Polski?’, *Chwile przelomu. 25 wydarzeń, które zmieniły dzieje Polski*, red. MARIA MAGDALENA MIŁASZEWSKA, Warszawa 2021, s. 129–134.

The foundation of noble liberty is considered to be the Nieszawa privileges granted by Casimir Jagiellon in 1554. Jagiellon, whose predecessors left him an empty treasury, lacked funds to conduct an independent policy and could not afford a hired army to confront the Teutonic Order. He therefore had to appeal to the nobility.

Unified laws for the nobility were published in 1487, combining the already issued provisions from the Wiślica and Piotrków statutes, the Warka statute of 28 October 1423, and the Nieszawa statutes of 1554, which formed the basis of noble freedom. This applied to the entire nobility, including the Crown and Lithuanian nobility. For the Lithuanian nobility, the Lithuanian statutes were crucial. These represented a codification of the law of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, a state that at the time encompassed lands of various peoples. The Statute of Lithuania of 1522 aimed to unify law in both civil and criminal matters and to adapt the legal system of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania to the changing socio-political conditions in the state governed by Sigismund I the Old³.

The project was prepared by outstanding lawyers educated at Western universities and approved by Sigismund I the Old on 29 September 1529 at the Sejm in Vilnius. The statute applied to all subjects of the capital of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania – Vilnius. From 1522 onward, the previous land privileges granted to the territories within the Grand Duchy of Lithuania by earlier Lithuanian princes ceased to be binding. Meanwhile, the rights and obligations of the princes, which limited central authority, were maintained. Like the Kingdom of Poland, Lithuania followed a path that privileged the nobility while limiting the power of the central, royal authority, a process that ultimately led to the construction of an oligarchic republic. From that moment, law was to be uniform throughout the state. The composition and competencies of the main state organs were regulated. Property rights and guarantees of personal inviolability for the Lithuanian nobility were established, modeled on the Polish system. The statute was intended as a comprehensive regula-

³ R. KOWALCZYK, 'Kobiety w przestrzeni społeczno-kulturalnej Rzeczypospolitej Obojga Narodów', *Міжкультурна комунікація*, № 35 (Луцьк, 2023): 23–27.

tion of the state and Lithuanian law, significant due to the historical traditions of the lands incorporated into Lithuania⁴.

The privileged social position of the nobility, at the expense of the burghers and peasants, became a path toward the anarchization of the state. Instead of building a strong institutional state, the supreme institution – the ruler – was deregulated in favor of the privileged nobility. This proved to be an irreversible process, ultimately leading to the partitions of Poland. The privileges strengthened the role of the magnate families, descended from the knightly estate. Continuous struggles between opposing political factions of the magnates (Tęczyński, Górka, Rytwiański, Koniecpolski, Oleśnicki families) and their omnipotence weakened the king's position in the country. The dominance of the magnates and the resulting chaos in the state became a source of discontent among the nobility. In this context, the royal court attempted to exploit the situation. Subsequent privileges were aimed at strengthening the position of the middle nobility. The nobility became an ally of the royal power against the magnate families. On the other hand, the magnates sought to gain influence over the nobility as an important player in Poland's evolving political system. The nobility began to play a clear political role, and both the court and the magnates had to reckon with its power. The late 15th and early 16th centuries therefore determined the shape of the state system, with the nobility playing a dominant role⁵.

⁴ M. BOGUĆKA, *Dawna Polska. Narodziny, rozkwit, upadek*, Warszawa, 1974, s. 87–91; J. MACISZEWSKI, *Szlachta polska i jej państwo*, Warszawa, 1969, s. 114–117; S. ROMAN, *Statuty nieszawskie*, Wrocław, 1957, s. 67–69; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Spory królów ze szlachtą w Złotym Wieku*, Kraków, 1988, s. 77–81; A. WY-
CZAŃSKI, *Szlachta polska XVI wieku*, Warszawa, 2021, s. 93–96.

⁵ M. BOGUĆKA, *Op. cit.*, s. 89–93; *Historia sejmu polskiego. Do schyłku szlacheckiej Rzeczypospolitej*, t. 1, red. JERZY MICHAŁSKI, Warszawa, 1984, s. 63–65; J. MACISZEWSKI, *Op. cit.*, s. 119–123; *Sejm Królestwa Polskiego i Rzeczypospolitej Obojga Narodów, a europejskie reprezentacje stanowe*, red. DARIUSZ KUPISZ, WACŁAW URUSZCZAK, Warszawa, 2019, s. 73–78; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Monarchia dwu ostatnich Jagiellonów a ruch egzekucyjny*, cz. 1, *Geneza egzekucji dóbr*, Wrocław i in., 1974, s. 44–47; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Spory królów ze szlachtą...*, s. 91–94; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Zygmunt August król Polski i wielki książę litewski*, Warszawa, 1996, s. 101–108.

From 1505 onward, the foundation of the Polish political system was the Sejm Walny, the general assembly consisting of the king, the senate, and the chamber of deputies. The Sejm became sovereign. Enactment of laws required the consent of the king, the senate, and the deputies. The Sejm represented a single social class – the nobility – excluding burghers and peasants, who had been removed from co-governing the state and subordinated to the omnipotence of the “noble nation”.

The nobility began striving for control over the state, a tendency expressed in the maintenance of an anachronistic military system – the *pospolite ruszenie*, based on the political power of the nobility. The nobility resisted the implementation of a modern tax system that would have enabled the organization of a regular, well-trained, and properly equipped army. They feared that a ruler with a strong army financed through regular taxation would seek to dismantle the entrenched system of governance, which relied on the so-called noble freedom – a system that in reality amounted to state anarchy and the self-rule of the nobility.

After the Union of Lublin in 1569, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth was transformed into a nobility republic, in which power was tied to membership in the noble estate. The “noble nation” accepted the weakness of the state. The lack of border defenses, the constant raids by Tatar hordes, the inefficiency of the supreme institution – the king and central authority – and the enormous material and human losses suffered by all social classes living in the borderlands – the nobility, peasants, and burghers – were deemed acceptable by the nobility. However, the majority of the nobility would not allow the strengthening of royal power or reforms that could modernize the Commonwealth. For the nobility, absolutism became the symbol of the end of their state – their Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. All initiatives from the royal camp aimed at modernizing the state, reforming the tax system to increase revenues, directing funds for the public good toward the expansion of a regular army, or improving the defensive system, were perceived by the nobility as attacks on their golden liberty and the beginning of the fall of their noble republic, potentially giving rise to absolutism. This perception

became a Sarmatian phobia, a unifying rallying cry for a heterogeneous noble estate defending the golden freedom and the noble state. The protection against any encroachment on noble liberty became ingrained in the noble mentality and, as the Commonwealth's anarchy deepened, became more important than concern for the failing state itself. A sense of superiority and historical mission led the nobility to pursue their estate interests without regard for the state or the general population, often at the expense of other estates – the burghers and peasants. By the sixteenth century, the nobility had secured complete economic independence for their privileged estate, subjugating peasants and depriving burghers of the opportunity to develop, stripping them of their economic rights, which had formed the foundation of strong towns. This was expressed in the instrumental treatment of burghers and peasants, whom the nobility contemptuously referred to as “elbows” and “churls”. In this way, the nobility transformed into the dominant social group in the life of the state. Consequently, a disastrous process emerged in the Commonwealth, in which the nobility came to perceive the state primarily as a source for realizing their own estate interests⁶.

Initially, the nobility benefited from the feudal economic system consolidated under the Jagiellonians. In the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth became an exporter of agricultural products, earning it the nickname the “granary of Europe”. The nobility took advantage of the high demand for grain and other agricultural goods in Western Europe, which was beginning to undergo economic transformations and lay the foundations for future industry, selling goods at a profit by transporting them to Gdańsk. At that time, Gdańsk, thanks to trade with the West – mainly through English and Dutch intermediaries – became one of the wealthiest cities in this part of Europe.

⁶ A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Monarchia dwu ostatnich Jagiellonów.*, s. 44–47; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Spory królów ze szlachtą.*, s. 91–94; A. SUCHENI-GRABOWSKA, *Zygmunt August.*, s. 101–108; J. MACISZEWSKI, *Op. cit.*, s. 119–123; A. WYCZAŃSKI, *Polska Rzeczpospolita szlachecką*, Warszawa, 1991, s. 89–94; A. WYCZAŃSKI, *Szlachta polska XVI wieku*, s. 102–106; R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Czy to Jagiellonowie doprowadzili do upadku Polski?’, s. 129–137.

However, this period of peak prosperity in the sixteenth and early seventeenth centuries sowed the seeds of the state's economic weakness. This was determined by the economic system that had developed in Poland in the fifteenth century, when the Jagiellonian – ruled state ultimately found itself in the eastern, feudal economic zone of Europe. Poland exported agricultural products and raw materials while importing finished goods and manufactured products from the emerging Western European economies of England and the Netherlands. The trade balance gradually deteriorated. Unfavorable developments in trade with the West occurred during the collapse of grain prices from the noble republic in the second half of the seventeenth century, but even in the sixteenth century, when considering trade with the East – including goods from the Middle East and Asia – the overall balance was disadvantageous for the Commonwealth. On the Moldavian route, the trade balance for Poland had already been negative from the mid-sixteenth century⁷.

With the growth of feudalism and the increasing privileged political, economic, and social role of the nobility, which was evolving into a “noble nation”, peasants were burdened with heavier feudal obligations, especially increased corvée labor, which became a key source of income for the nobility. This caused discontent among peasants, deprived of opportunities for development, who fled from the lands of Ukraine, Lithuania, and Poland to the uninhabited southern regions of Ukraine, known as the Wild Fields. This exodus was related to restrictions on their freedoms imposed by the nobility, a class that increasingly and rigorously enforced rights granted by the Jagiellonian dynasty. For peasants unwilling to accept the reduction of their relatively broad rights, still present in the fifteenth century, escape remained the only option.

These fleeing peasants joined a multiethnic community known as the Cossacks, called Niżowcy at the time. As their numbers grew, they created an unprecedented European society based on military

⁷ R. RYBARI, *Handel i polityka handlowa Polski w XVI stuleciu*, t. 1, Poznań, 1928–1929, s. 157–164; t. 2, s. 67–75; J. TOPOLSKI, *Gospodarka polska a europejska w XVI–XVIII w.*, Poznań, 1977, s. 123–129.

democracy. From the outset, the Cossacks pursued their own interests, forming alliances with Moscow, the Commonwealth, or the Crimean Khanate as it suited them. They became an important political and military actor in this part of Europe.

The Kaniv starosta – a Cossack magnate and administrator of Braclav, Vinnycia, Cherkasy, and Kaniv – organized the Ukrainian Cossacks and founded the Zaporizhian Sich on Chortytsia Island in the Dnieper, which he fortified specifically for this purpose. He independently launched expeditions to the Crimea. In retaliation for the destruction of Braclav by Khan Devlet Giray, he, together with the Poles, devastated numerous Tatar settlements near Ochakiv and later captured the fortress of Aslan-Kermen at the Dnieper estuary. Although his death was tragic – Sultan Suleiman the Magnificent of the Ottoman Empire condemned him to a prolonged and agonizing execution – his creation, the Zaporizhian Sich, survived. Even after its destruction, it continued to develop, and soon after its fall, Dmytro Vyshnevecki, undeterred by Tatar retaliation, founded a new Sich – this time on Monastery Island⁸.

The emergence of the Cossacks on the southeastern frontiers of Lithuania, and after the Union of Lublin in 1569, in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, was closely linked to the weakness of the ruling powers – initially the Jagiellonian dynasty and subsequently the elective monarchs. The Polish state, supporting Lithuania, was exposed to constant pressure from the east by the rising power of Moscow. Although Polish forces managed to repel Muscovite raids, the territories under Lithuanian control had been steadily shrinking since the late fifteenth century. This was largely due to the privileged position of the nobility in the Polish state, a position further reinforced under Jagiellonian rule.

Although the sixteenth century is often regarded as the “golden age” in Polish history, in reality it marked the beginning of the

⁸ R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Sicz Zaporoska w drugiej połowie XVI stulecia i w wieku XVII. Narodziny i upadek wolnej Kozaczyzny zaporoskiej – istotnego podmiotu polityczno-wojskowego w rejonie Morza Czarnego’, *Козацька скарбниця. Гетьманські читання*, К., 2017, с. 36–43.

Polish state's decline. Louis I of Hungary initiated the process, and Władysław Jagiełło, determined to secure power in Poland for his dynasty, further developed it, fundamentally altering the course of the state's history. Noble privileges transformed the nobility into a nation – remarkably, the only nation in the state. Ignoring broader consequences, the Jagiellonians subordinated other social classes to the political and economic interests of the nobility. Over time, the nobility progressively appropriated the economic rights of the burghers, gained dominance over their estate, and curtailed the freedoms of the peasants, pushing them into the constraints of feudal labor obligations, particularly serfdom. The Polish state thereby lost the potential to develop a modern system that it had still retained in the fifteenth century.

The nobility also obtained extensive judicial privileges. The dominance of the “noble nation” ultimately led to the decline of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Expressions of state anarchy included privileges that favored the nobility at the expense of the burghers and peasants. These included, among others: the so-called provincial taxes, where urban product prices were set by a voivode drawn from the noble class; the equalization of Polish and Lithuanian noble rights; personal immunity from judgment without a verdict; the requirement that no new taxes or laws be imposed without the consent of local noble assemblies (*sejmiks*); harsher penalties for peasants fleeing villages; restrictions on peasants leaving the land, ultimately allowing only one peasant per village to leave each year; exemption from duties on goods produced in noble estates; and a ban on burghers purchasing land.

The ruler relinquished jurisdiction over disputes between secular and ecclesiastical lords and their subjects, while municipal courts lost authority when the perpetrator was a noble. Additionally, the king was prohibited from removing nobles from office. At the same time, the nobility, wishing to maintain control over the state, sought to preserve an anachronistic military system based on their political power – the *pospolite ruszenie*. The nobility opposed the introduction of a modern tax system that could finance a standing,

well-trained, and properly equipped army. They feared that a ruler with such a force would dismantle the anachronistic system of governance, which relied on the so-called noble freedom, a system that in reality amounted to state anarchy, the self-rule of the noble estate controlled by magnates, and through them, by foreign powers.

Thus, the weakness of the state, the absence of a standing army, Tatar raids, and human and material losses were tolerated, as long as the monarch was not strengthened. The specter of absolutism – comparable to that of the Grand Duchy of Moscow – was seen as the ultimate threat to the noble republic, a symbol of the end of the Commonwealth⁹.

As a result, the weak Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, due to its small standing army, was unable to effectively defend its borders or protect its inhabitants from raids by nomads from the Crimea. It was also incapable of permanently repelling the rising power of Moscow. On the other hand, the increasing oppression and exploitation of peasants by the nobility caused mass flight. Peasants from Ukraine, Poland, and Lithuania fled to the uninhabited southern regions of Ukraine, known as the Wild Fields. The weakness of the state meant that the fugitives found safety there and, most importantly, freedom from noble exploitation.

These refugees gradually formed a multiethnic community known as the Cossacks. As their numbers grew, they created a society unprecedented in Europe, based on a form of military democracy. From the moment they became a permanent force, the Cossacks pursued their own interests, forming alliances either with Moscow, the Commonwealth, or the Crimean Khanate. They became a significant political and military actor in the Black Sea region, which in the seventeenth century determined dominance over much of Central and Eastern Europe.

The coexistence of the Zaporozhian Cossacks with the Poles within the weak Commonwealth revealed conflicting interests.

⁹ J. MACISZEWSKI, *Op. cit.*, s. 119–123; A. WYCZAŃSKI, *Polska Rzeczpospolita szlachecka*, s. 89–94; R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Czy to Jagiellonowie doprowadzili do upadku Polski?’, s. 129–137.

There were no enduring common goals; only temporary alliances could be formed, typically in response to a shared threat – such as the powerful Ottoman Empire or its vassal, the Crimean Khanate. The Cossack community sought to preserve its freedom at all costs. Living on the borderlands, in the no-man’s-land of the Wild Fields, their existence depended on warfare against the Ottoman Empire and the Tatars. Profits from raiding were essential for their survival. Cossack expeditions on chaikas penetrated deep into Ottoman territory. They captured and destroyed Ottoman towns along the Black Sea, attacked Tatar villages, disrupted Black Sea trade, captured numerous ships, and even attacked the outskirts of Istanbul itself.

The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, with its military weakness and lack of a stable taxation system capable of funding a regular army, was reliant on the Cossacks. With no resources for a permanent standing army, the Cossacks became an ideal partner. In times of border threat – whether from Tatar raids or direct conflict with the Ottoman Empire – they supported the Commonwealth’s forces. Crown Hetmans and magnates pursuing their interests in the southeastern Commonwealth used the Cossacks’ military strength to conduct preventive strikes against Turkish holdings in the Black Sea region, reducing the threat to the Commonwealth’s lands. The Cossacks also participated in private expeditions organized by magnates to enforce pro-Polish policies in the Danubian Principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia. Magnates sought to establish these states as buffer zones against the Turks and Tatars, and the Cossacks willingly joined these operations. They were well-compensated and hoped to be integrated into the Commonwealth’s regular forces, securing stable income for their military skills. However, the nature of the Polish state – the noble republic – posed a structural problem. The Commonwealth was a state of one nation – the “noble nation” – comprising Poles, Lithuanians, and Ukrainians. The landowning classes – the nobility, landed gentry, and magnates holding vast estates in Ukraine – underwent Polonization, which served their interests. Culture and economic life flowed from Warsaw. The “noble nation” – Poles, Lithuanians, and Ukrainians – shared common in-

terests. There were no national divisions; all considered themselves part of the “chosen nation”, the only group entitled to the privileges of the Commonwealth. Only the nobility – the single nation – could represent the state and enjoy the benefits of its feudal system, which subordinated peasants and marginalized the urban population¹⁰.

Consequently, the Cossacks were not viewed as equals within the Commonwealth. They were valued allies, useful for repelling Muslim invasions and limiting destructive attacks, but no member of the “noble nation” seriously considered incorporating them into the governance structures of the Commonwealth. One notable exception was Adam Świątoldycz – Swiatold Kisiel, voivode of Kyiv and Braclav. Though a member of the elite, a magnate from south-eastern Ukraine, he resisted the cultural influence emanating from Warsaw, maintained his Ukrainian Orthodox faith, and preserved local traditions. He was highly respected both in Warsaw and among the Cossack camp of Bohdan Khmelnytsky¹¹.

The Cossacks were utilized and generously rewarded when there was a need to fight the Tatar hordes or the Ottoman power, but no one considered accommodating their political aspirations within the state of the chosen nation – the noble Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth – at least not until the successes of the Cossacks in Bohdan Khmelnytsky’s uprising. The Commonwealth sought to employ the increasingly powerful Zaporozhian Cossacks to combat Tatars and Turks, serving its own objectives, yet integrating the Cossacks into the defense system conflicted with the goals of the

¹⁰ W. SERCZYK, *Na dalekiej Ukrainie. Dzieje Kozaczyzny do 1648 roku*, Kraków, 1984, s. 81–83, 122–124; С. ЛЕП’ЯВКО, *Українське козацтво у міжнародних відносинах (1561–1591)*, Чернівці, 1999, с. 119–139; С. ЛЕП’ЯВКО, *Козацькі війни кінця XVI ст. в Україні*, Чернівці, 1996, с. 47–49; H. LIŹWIN, *Naręyw szlachty polskiej na Ukrainę 1569–1648*, Warszawa, 2000, s. 20–28; N. JAKOWENKO, *Historia Ukrainy do 1795 roku*, Warszawa, 2011, s. 67–74; Z. WÓJCIK, *Dzikie Pola w ogniu. O Kozaczyźnie w dawnej Rzeczypospolitej*, Warszawa, 1960, s. 88–97; Z. WÓJCIK, *Wojny kozackie w dawnej Polsce*, Kraków, 1989, s. 71–74; K. GRÜNBERG, B. SPRENGEL, *Trudne sąsiedztwo. Stosunki polsko-ukraińskie w X–XX wieku*, Warszawa, 2005, s. 114–118.

¹¹ F. E. SYSYN, *Between Poland and Ukraine: The dilemma of Adam Kysil 1600–1653*, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1985, p. 128–139.

nobility and their state – the noble Commonwealth. To the nobility, the Cossacks were an ethnically and socially alien element. Moreover, from the perspective of the nobles, incorporating them in large numbers into the Commonwealth's forces raised concerns that the Cossacks might align with the king and challenge the nobles' "freedom", anarchy, and dominance, which were the greatest assets of the magnates and the noble masses they manipulated. Consequently, the Commonwealth required the Cossacks only during wartime. In peacetime, the Cossacks were unnecessary, even unwelcome. Warsaw, in order to maintain peace along the southeastern borderlands, was compelled to restrain Zaporozhian Cossack raids on Ottoman territory. During periods of peace treaties and stable relations between the state and the Crimean Khanate or the Ottoman Empire, Cossack raids generated conflicts between the Crimea, Turkey, and the Commonwealth. The noble Commonwealth was too weak and inefficient to prevent such expeditions.

At the same time, the Commonwealth was unaware of the changes occurring within the Sich. The Cossacks had ceased to be merely a military force. Organized around military democracy, they developed elites that sought to leverage their strength. By the first half of the seventeenth century, the Zaporozhian Cossacks had grown into a significant military power. Yet they remained purely martial, aware of their military might but not of their political potential. They did not realize that the most effective means of exerting influence over the Commonwealth would be to integrate into the chosen nation – the nobility. Any Cossack contingent, no matter how large, was merely a military service for the Commonwealth. Neither the Cossacks regarded the Commonwealth as their state, nor did the Poles view the Cossacks as equal partners. Although Ukraine was jointly defended – with state – paid Polish troops and registered Cossacks – the Cossacks saw themselves as a military – political elite, focusing solely on maximizing the number of registered Cossacks and emphasizing their military strength.

Within the "noble nation", even among those from Ukraine, there was a prevailing perception that the Cossacks were armed pea-

sants. The nobility, for its part, despised peasants. The resulting discord and lack of understanding – that both Poles of the “noble nation” and the Cossacks shared a common state and that mutual coexistence could foster a common ground of interests – found no recognition on either side. The tragedy of this coexistence within the Commonwealth was compounded by the fact that the Cossacks, considering themselves an elite, looked down upon Ukrainian peasants, whom they called the ‘czerní’ (chern). Consequently, the Cossacks showed no compassion for their Ukrainian peasant brothers – men, women, children, and the elderly – who were captured and killed by Tatar raiding parties conducting pillaging raids along the Commonwealth’s borders. This dynamic became fully evident during Khmelnytsky’s uprising. Pursuing their particular interests and ensuring that their Tatar allies remained loyal and cooperated in attacking the Poles, the Cossacks handed over thousands of Ukrainian peasants. At that time, none of the Cossacks considered the fate of their Ukrainian peasant brethren, driven thousands of kilometers and sold cheaply to Muslims in slave markets. The mutual approach of the Poles – the “noble nation” – and the Cossacks resulted in a sea of blood and a chasm that ultimately led both Poland and Ukraine into the hands of Moscow¹².

Although there were instances of cooperation, they were never politically leveraged. The Poles acted primarily according to military needs; the Cossacks were necessary as a military force, without whom it was often difficult to defend the borders of the Commonwealth from Tatar raids or even from the full force of the Ottoman Empire, as in 1621. The Cossacks considered actions on behalf of the Commonwealth as a way to encourage Warsaw to increase the number of registered Cossacks paid from the Commonwealth’s budget. Furthermore, their very existence relied on raids against Tatar

¹² W. TOMKIEWICZ, ‘O składzie społecznym i etnicznym Kozaczyzny Ukrainnej na przełomie XVI i XVII wieku’, *Przegląd Historyczny*, t. 37 (1948): 249–260; N. JAKOWENKO, *Historia Ukrainy..*, s. 142–144; L. PODHORODECKI, *Sicz Zaporowska*, Warszawa, 1960, s. 64–67; L. PODHORODECKI, *Zarys dziejów Ukrainy*, Warszawa, 1976, s. 53–56.

and Turkish holdings along the Black Sea, so any weakening of the Tatars or Turks was advantageous to them.

One example of such cooperation occurred in 1594. At that time, Khan Gazi II Girey launched a campaign against the Commonwealth using guides provided by the Moldavian hospodar Aron. On the initiative of the Grand Crown Hetman Jan Zamoyski, the Cossacks, commanded by Hetman Bohdan Mikosiński and operating in Zaporozhian chaikas, attempted to prevent the Tatars from crossing the Dnieper near Ochakiv. Although they were unable to stop them, the Zaporozhian Cossacks did everything in their power to support the actions of Grand Hetman Jan Zamoyski.

The absence of sustained, mutual pursuit of common interests for the benefit of both parties and the shared state in which they lived was exemplified by the Treaty of 16 July 1607 between the Ottoman Empire and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. After many years, both sides had reached a common understanding to maintain peace along the burning frontier. Peace was to return to the southeastern borders of the Commonwealth. However, the treaty's foundation was unstable. The Poles knew they could not prevent Cossack raids. The Commonwealth lacked the strength and capacity to restrain the Cossacks along the Black Sea coast. Similarly, the Turks could not prevent Tatar raids. The Crimean Khanate was then too independent for the Ottomans to restrain Tatar expeditions into the southeastern territories of the Commonwealth, which included not only Tatars but also various border populations: Vallakhians, Moldavians, Gypsies, Hungarians, and Muscovites. These marauding raids could not be stopped.

Both sides therefore committed to obligations that were virtually impossible to enforce. Nevertheless, good relations with the Turks were crucial for the Commonwealth, as a war with Russia was imminent. The Commonwealth relied on an alliance with the Crimean Khanate and cooperation against Russia. For the Gireys – the Crimean Khans – maintaining a calm frontier was also in their interest. The Muscovite state was very weak, and plundering raids deep into its territory were virtually unpunished even for relatively

small Tatar bands. Shared interests and competition for dominance in the Black Sea region led the Commonwealth and the Crimean Khanate to sign an alliance and direct their forces against a common, most dangerous enemy – Moscow. The alliance benefited both parties: the Commonwealth received military support, and the Tatars could freely raid the weakened Muscovite state. Enormous numbers of captives were taken to Crimea, filling slave markets in the Middle and Near East, causing slave prices to plummet. For the Crimean Khanate, both for the state authorities and private intermediaries profiting from the slave trade, this was a period of prosperity.

However, the alliance with the Tatars could not last long. The Zaporozhian Cossacks were not integrated into the Commonwealth's system of war profits linked to participation in the campaign against Moscow. The number of registered Cossacks was not increased, and within the Sich there was no awareness that Moscow was the most dangerous adversary. The only thing that mattered was plunder. Consequently, Cossack activity intensified. Aware of the significant engagement of Tatar forces against the powerless Muscovite state, the Cossacks captured Perekop in 1608 and raided Tatar estates reaching Bilgorod a year later. They did not hesitate to attack Turkish provinces either. The Black Sea coasts burned with Cossack daring. They repeatedly reached the outskirts of Istanbul. Turkish naval patrols were ineffective. The Cossacks, operating in chaikas, were extremely effective yet nearly untouchable. In 1616, they carried out a bold raid on Crimea, destroying dozens of Tatar settlements. They obliterated a Turkish flotilla and captured and plundered the wealthy city of Kaffa, liberating thousands of Christian captives gathered there by the Tatars and prepared for shipment to Asian markets¹³.

This led to further tensions along the Istanbul-Warsaw axis, which were exacerbated by the Commonwealth's alliance with the Habsburgs in 1613. Nevertheless, despite being weakened by con-

¹³ L. PODHORODECKI, *Siecz Zaporoska*, s. 67–73; L. PODHORODECKI, *Zarys dziejów Ukrainy*, s. 58–66; L. PODHORODECKI, *Chanat krymski i jego stosunki z Polską w XV–XVIII wieku*, s. 143–158; R. ROMAŃSKI, *Kozaczyzna*, Warszawa, 2004, s. 75–81.

federations following the war with Russia, the Commonwealth, under the leadership of Grand Crown Hetman Stanisław Żółkiewski, was able to assemble forces that compelled the Turks to conclude the Treaty of Busza on the Dniester on 23 September 1617. Once again, the treaty included a provision emphasized by the Turks, requiring the Commonwealth to address the raiding activities of the Zaporozhian Cossacks that disrupted Ottoman interests. At that time, the Cossacks were commanded by one of the most distinguished Cossack hetmans – Petro Konashevych-Sahaidachny, an icon of Ukrainian history.

Sahaidachny actively supported the Poles in the war against Moscow. The Cossacks participated in two campaigns against Moscow in 1613 and 1618. Despite such significant engagement and the close relationship between Hetman Sahaidachny and Crown Prince Władysław, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, concerned about retaliatory Tatar raids and strained relations with the Ottoman Empire, decided to reduce the number of registered Cossacks. This was a short-sighted policy, as the threat of war with Turkey had not diminished, and the Cossacks were treated instrumentally. Following this decision, tensions between Poland and the Ottoman Empire remained high. The provisions of the Busza treaty were largely ineffective in maintaining peaceful relations.

The turning point came in 1620. Early in the year, the Cossacks organized several successful raids on the Black Sea, reaching the outskirts of Istanbul, which they set ablaze. The defeat of the Polish forces at Cecora and the death of the elderly Hetman Stanisław Żółkiewski left the southeastern provinces of the Commonwealth defenseless before the Tatar hordes. From Podillia, Volhynia, Red Ruthenia, and Przemyśl lands, the Tatars captured thousands of slaves without resistance. The following year, 1621, saw joint military action by the Commonwealth and the Cossacks against the Ottoman-Tatar onslaught. Hetman Sahaidachny did not abandon the Poles in their hour of need. He was one of the most outstanding Cossack leaders, with foresight regarding the future of the Cossacks. He understood that the Cossacks lived within the Polish-Lithuanian

Monument to Hetman Petro Konashevych-Sahajdachny, an icon of Ukrainian history. The hetman pursued an active policy, believing that the Cossack Sich and the independence of the Cossacks could only exist within the framework of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. The system of a republic of the elected nation – the noble estate, the weakness of central institutions and the lack of a permanent army allowed for the independence of the Cossack Sich. Hetman Konaszewicz-Sahajdachny supported the Poles in their war with Moscow. The Cossacks took part in two expeditions to Moscow in 1613 and 1618. At Chocim in 1621, Hetman Konaszewicz-Sahajdachny's 30,000-strong Cossack corps saved the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth from a Turkish-Tatar invasion led directly by Sultan Osman II and Tatar Khan Dżanibek Gereja II. Without the Cossack troops, Grand Hetman of Lithuania Jan Karol Chodkiewicz would not have been able to defend the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth from the Turkish-Tatar invasion. Unfortunately, after 1621, the noble nation did not sober up. The great deed of the Cossacks in supporting and defending them was forgotten. The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth did not expand the number of registered Cossacks. The blame lay with the nobility, who, blinded by the idea of a noble republic, i.e. an exploiting elite, did not want to pay taxes for the army. There were no taxes for the Crown army, nor for the registered Cossack army. The wasted opportunity for cooperation between the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth and the Sich Cossacks was not to be repeated. Sinking into ever greater chaos and the progressive weakness of its central institutions, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth drowned successive armed uprisings of the Cossacks in blood, until fratricidal fighting broke out in 1648. The winner was Moscow, which took advantage of the Cossack-Polish fighting and dominated, and then liquidated, the Hetmanate and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Photo with the author. Kyiv 2018.

Commonwealth and that its enemies were simultaneously enemies of the Cossacks. He was fully aware that in no other political entity in the Black Sea region would an independent Sich, an elite military-political Cossack body, have a chance to function. For this reason, he sought to establish a platform of understanding with the nobility, creating a stable basis for mutual Polish-Cossack interests.

Consequently, recognizing the threat to the functioning of the Commonwealth following Żółkiewski's defeat at Cecora, he chose to support the Poles, who, without aid from any other Christian states in Europe, were attempting to resist the Turkish-Tatar onslaught. The Cossacks, together with the Polish-Lithuanian forces commanded by Grand Hetman Jan Karol Chodkiewicz, entrenched themselves in a fortified camp at Chotyn. Sahaidachny's Cossacks and the Commonwealth's troops jointly repelled the Turkish-Tatar offensive, commanded personally by Sultan Osman II and Tatar Khan Janibek Girey II. Hetman Sahaidachny brought a Cossack corps of 30,000, outnumbering the Polish-Lithuanian contingent. Without the support of Sahaidachny's Cossacks, halting the massive army personally led by Sultan Osman II would have been impossible¹⁴.

Unfortunately, after the Ottoman threat subsided in 1621, the Commonwealth did nothing to address the emerging Cossack issue. The growth in the number of Cossacks participating in campaigns against Moscow and in the defense against the Turkish-Tatar onslaught of 1621 meant an increase in the Cossacks' importance and their role in the Commonwealth. It became clear that it was not the Polish units or the *pospolite ruszenie*, but the Cossacks who saved the state – the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth of the chosen nation, the nobility. Moreover, such forces under royal command could threaten the prevailing system in the Commonwealth. The nobility feared that the king would gain an instrument to challenge anarchy, the inefficient tax system, and the overwhelming power of the nobility within the state. A stronger and larger corps of registered Cossacks could strengthen the king's position and modernize the state. This was unacceptable to the nobility. The chosen nation – the no-

¹⁴ Р. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Роль Кримського Ханату як гаранта рівноваги сил у Причорномор'ї на межі XVI–XVII ст.', *Наш Крим*, вип. V (К., 2022): 151–156.

bility – accepted state weakness, lack of a standing army, an inefficient judicial system, lawlessness, and even the losses resulting from repeated Tatar raids on the Commonwealth's borders, but under no circumstances would they accept any limitation on their privileges, which sustained the inefficiency of the state. Consequently, a strong Cossack corps serving the Commonwealth was unacceptable to the nobility. The nobility feared both absolutism and strong royal power, as well as the Cossacks, who might safeguard the system they depended on.

As a result, among the elites of the Commonwealth there was no will to resolve the Cossack issue positively in a way that would satisfy both sides. Consequently, the Cossack problem was essentially covered over without any real action. Yet the issue persisted – it remained dynamic, pulsating, and increasingly significant within the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Among the Cossacks, there were no leaders of the caliber of Hetman Sahaidachny. The death of Hetman Sahaidachny allowed the nobility – unfavorable toward the Cossacks, living within the noble mentality, confident in the power of the Commonwealth, and convinced of the nobility's supremacy over other social estates – to freeze the issue, leaving it for subsequent generations.

The following years demonstrated clearly that the Cossacks had evolved beyond merely a military force: they had become a political power, making decisions according to their own interests – broadly speaking, the interests of the political center of the Zaporozhian Sich. This development eventually erupted with force, weakening the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth to a degree from which it never fully recovered before 1648¹⁵.

An example of this autonomy was the engagement of the Cossacks on the side of Mehmed II and the reversal of the situation in the Crimean Khanate, where the forces of the Turkish vizier Rzhedzib had already reinstated the authority of Khan Janibek II Girey under Ottoman suzerainty. The Cossacks, who had entered into a formal alliance with a foreign power – the Crimean state represented by

¹⁵ Р. КОВАЛЬНИК, 'Роль Кримського Ханату...', с. 151–156.

the rebel Mehmed II Girey and Shahin Girey, who even reached the court of Shah Abbas the Great of Persia seeking support against the Ottoman Empire – did not merely defeat the Turkish forces of vizier Rzhedzib on the Crimean Peninsula; they also overthrew Mehmed II Girey’s authority. The independent engagement of the Cossacks in the struggle for control over the Crimean Khanate was a clear manifestation of the Zaporozhian Sich’s increasing political autonomy and influence¹⁶.

In this context, the Poles, as after their victory over Sultan Osman II, did not offer the Cossacks cooperation, nor did they attempt to channel the Cossacks’ political activity toward shared governance for the benefit of the state in which they coexisted – the Commonwealth. This was dictated by the nobility – the magnates, the “chosen nation”. The Crown forces, under Grand Crown Hetman Stanisław Koniecpolski, were sent against the Cossacks. The treaty signed on 6 November 1625 near Lake Kurukove formalized this: the Zaporozhian Cossacks submitted to the Commonwealth, and the Sich renounced conducting an independent foreign policy. However, the agreement guaranteed nothing; it was a temporary measure – a pause, a time to consolidate forces. The Cossacks recognized this period as an opportunity to regroup and pursue their objectives, now no longer shared with the Commonwealth, but autonomously as the Zaporozhian Sich – a decision-making body gradually evolving into a nucleus of an independent state amid growing animosities with Warsaw. The Cossacks had no choice. The Poles – the “noble nation”, the Commonwealth – did not allow them to pursue political and military goals jointly, in peaceful coexistence that would benefit the power of a unified state, comprising Poles, Lithuanians, Ukrainianized magnates, the nobility, and Cossacks alike. Subsequent Cossack uprisings fully demonstrated this reality¹⁷.

¹⁶ Р. КОВАЛЬЧИК, ‘Роль Кримського Ханату...’, с. 149–154.

¹⁷ N. JAKOWENKO, *Historia Ukrainy...*, s. 142–144; L. PODHORODECKI, *Sicz Zaporoska*, s. 67–73; L. PODHORODECKI, *Zarys dziejów Ukrainy*, s. 58–66; L. PODHORODECKI, *Chanat krymski i jego stosunki z Polską w XV–XVIII wieku*, s. 143–158; R. ROMAŃSKI, *Kozaczyzna*, s. 75–81; R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Sicz Zaporoska w drugiej połowie XVI stulecia...’, с. 42–63.

The outbreak of Bohdan Khmelnytsky's uprising in 1648 reflected the escalating problem, the growing political consciousness of the Cossacks, and the desire of the Sich to act as a political center. The uprising illustrated the rising significance of the Zaporozhian Cossacks. Meanwhile, the alliance with the Tatars signified the political independence of the Sich. The Cossacks drew lessons from uprisings in which they had participated since the death of Hetman Sahaidachny. They recognized that the Tatars could assist in defeating the forces of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Only after victories over the Poles did the Cossacks consolidate a state from the territories inhabited by Ukrainians and Cossacks, which until 1648 had been part of the Commonwealth. Victories at Zhovti Vody and Korsun, resulting from the disastrously commanded forces of Grand Crown Hetman Mikołaj Potocki, handed Ukraine into the hands of the Cossacks. Under the leadership of Bohdan Khmelnytsky, they began establishing an independent state.

The costs of this political entity were immense. The alliance with the Tatars caused massive destruction. Thousands of inhabitants of Ukraine – Polish nobility, townspeople, and Ukrainian peasants alike – were killed. Tens of thousands of Ukrainians were taken to the slave markets of Crimea. Cities, villages, and farmsteads were destroyed; all of this was the consequence of extremely brutal military operations in Ukraine.

Ukraine was key to achieving power in the Black Sea region and subsequently gaining primacy in Central and Eastern Europe. The enemies of the Poles and Ukrainians – Muscovites – were fully aware of Ukraine's strategic importance. Since the sixteenth century, the Crimean Khanate, Muscovy, the Commonwealth, and the Ottoman Empire had been contesting this primacy. Until 1648, relative stability prevailed. In the latter half of the fifteenth century, the Muscovites had not only repelled devastating Tatar invasions from Crimea but had also occupied the Astrakhan and Kazan Khanates, inheriting the legacy of the Golden Horde. Due to the animosity between the Crimean Khanate and the Commonwealth, Moscow could not be permanently weakened during the Time of Troubles. The Ro-

manov Muscovy consolidated power and decided to seize the historical opportunity to subjugate the Commonwealth and take control of Ukraine. Moscow exploited the weakness of the Commonwealth and the growing antagonism between the Cossacks and the Poles.

During the Polish-Cossack wars and Bohdan Khmelnytsky's uprising, the Muscovites closely observed the shifting situation. The Hetmanate, established by Khmelnytsky following victorious campaigns against the Commonwealth and formalized by the Zboriv Treaty of 1649 with the newly elected King Jan Kazimierz and the Commonwealth, did not guarantee the Cossacks' continued independence in the territories they had occupied. Subsequent years of war with the Commonwealth, which sought to reclaim lost lands at all costs, demonstrated this. The Tsar of Muscovy, Alexey I Mikhailovich, exploiting the escalating conflict between Poles and Ukrainians, intervened in the civil war by signing an agreement with the Hetmanate. On 18 January 1654, in Pereiaslav, the Tsar's plenipotentiary, Vasily Vasilyevich Buturlin, concluded a treaty with the Hetmanate and Bohdan Khmelnytsky. It was purely a military agreement, yet from the outset Moscow claimed that it represented Ukraine's submission to Muscovite suzerainty. Among the Zaporozhian forces, many commanders refused to accept the agreement with Moscow. Time proved them correct. Khmelnytsky, pursuing immediate military-political objectives, altered the trajectory of the Hetmanate's development. The newly formed Hetmanate never regained independence from Muscovy. Moscow fully understood that subjugating Ukraine, occupying the western Ukrainian lands, and later Polish territories would allow Muscovy to emerge as a great power. The Pereiaslav agreement marked the beginning of the Russo-Polish war, and Left-Bank Ukraine was occupied by Muscovite forces, never returning to the Commonwealth.

Although, theoretically, the role of the Commonwealth had been diminished in the context of the emergence of the Zaporozhian Cossack polity as a leading political-military center in the Black Sea region, the second half of the seventeenth century represented an attempt to restore Ukraine, albeit under a new political configuration.

It was only then that within the Commonwealth did elites advocating a vision of a three – nation Commonwealth – Poles, Lithuanians, and Cossacks, rather than the previously dominant Ukrainianized magnates and nobility – come to the fore. This attempt occurred after Bohdan Khmelnytsky's death. Khmelnytsky had left the Hetmanate in a difficult position, without strong support for his son, and with the Cossack seniority divided into factions. At that time, authority in the Dnieper Ukraine was exercised on behalf of the underage Yurii Khmelnytsky by Hetman Ivan Vyhovsky¹⁸. Vyhovsky supported reconciliation with the Commonwealth, motivated by political calculation. He recognized Moscow's pressure on Ukraine and sought to guide the country through the difficult period following Khmelnytsky's death, maintain the independence of the young Ukrainian state, and preserve the established social order, including the landed estates of the Cossack elite. He believed this could be achieved through an alliance with the Commonwealth. Muscovy, however, was a highly centralized state, with strong central institutions dominated by the tsar and the Romanov dynasty, to which all institutions and society were subordinated. Since the signing of the Pereiaslav agreement, Muscovy sought to bring Ukraine and the Hetmanate under its control. Hetman Vyhovsky fully understood this. Meanwhile, the Tatars could serve as effective military allies, but not political partners. The growing dependence of the Girays on the Ottoman Porte, combined with cultural, religious, and political differences, precluded such coexistence. By 1657, Hetman Vyhovsky saw no feasible option for political collaboration¹⁹.

¹⁸ R. KOWALCZYK, 'Polacy i Ukraińcy dwa bratanki, czyli dlaczego nie udało stworzyć się zeczpospolitej Trojga Narodów i powstrzymać państwa moskiewskiego w ekspansji na zachód', [w:] *Społeczeństwo w wojsku, wojsko w społeczeństwie w XIX–XXI wieku*, t. 1, red. M. KRUSZYŃSKI, P. ORŁOWSKI, T. OSIŃSKI, Dęblin 2024, s. 35.

¹⁹ L. PODHORODECKI, *Sicz Zaporoska*, s. 67–73; L. PODHORODECKI, *Zarys dziejów Ukrainy*, s. 58–66; R. ROMAŃSKI, *Kozaczyzna*, s. 75–81; Z. WÓJCİK, *Wojny kozackie w dawnej Polce*, s. 89–102; J. KACZMARCZYK, *Bohdan Chmielnicki*, Wrocław i in., 1988, s. 67–98; W. A. SERCZYK, *Na płonącej Ukrainie. Dzieje Kozaczyzny 1648–1651*, Warszawa, 1998, s. 102–114; N. JAKOWENKO, *Historia Ukrainy...*, s. 135–149; J. BESALA, *Wielcy Hetmani Rzeczypospolitej*, Warszawa, 1983,

Hetman Ivan Vyhovsky, however, faced a difficult task. The structural problem of the state remained unresolved: the Hetmanate had not developed strong central institutions capable of making the state resilient to external threats. Its decentralization meant that Muscovy could easily bribe members of the Cossack elite and provoke a revolt against legally functioning Hetmanate authorities whenever independence was pursued.

As a result, almost immediately after Vyhovsky's election, in the autumn of 1657, a popular uprising broke out among Ukrainians, centered in the Poltava region. The revolt targeted the social relations established in the Hetmanate following the expulsion of the Polish nobility from Ukraine. In the Hetmanate, the pre-existing social structure from the Commonwealth era remained largely intact; only the landowners changed. The estates were taken over by the Cossack elite – the starshyna. The insurgents demanded the restoration of traditional Cossack liberties: the unrestricted right to distill vodka, unrestricted rights to hunt and fish, free movement to the Zaporizhian lands, and the election of the Hetman by the so-called Chorna Rada (Black Council), in which, alongside the wealthy Cossack elite, ordinary Cossacks and Ukrainian peasants – the 'czerní' or lower rank – had equal voting rights.

At the same time, Martyn Pushkar, a rival to Vyhovsky and a supporter of a faction of the Cossack starshyna favoring political and military alliance with Muscovy, openly opposed Vyhovsky. This sparked a civil war that would decide the orientation of Ukraine and the Hetmanate: toward Muscovy or the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. With the support and silver coins of Muscovy, Pushkar easily gained the backing of the *koshovyi* ataman Yakiv Barabash. Propaganda proved effective. Pushkar assumed leadership of the popular uprising known as the *deinek* – a movement of the lower – class Ukrainian populace, centered in the Poltava region, that erupted in the autumn of 1657. The radical social demands and dissatisfaction

s. 257–269; *Hetmani Rzeczypospolitej Obojga Narodów*, pod red. M. NAGIELSKI, Warszawa, 1995, s. 134–147; *Hetmani zaporoscy w służbie króla i Rzeczypospolitej*, red. P. KROLL, M. NAGIELSKI, M. WAGNER, Zabrze, 2010, s. 226–244.

of the nizovtsy led Ukrainians and Cossacks under propaganda influence to rise against Hetman Vyhovsky's authority²⁰.

Vyhovsky, after unsuccessful attempts at reconciliation, decided to suppress the rebellion by force to protect the Hetmanate. The main battles took place in the Poltava region. Pushkar fled to Poltava, but his forces were defeated in a battle on the city's outskirts on 11 June 1658. Muscovy attempted to rescue Ataman Barabash; he initially managed to escape under the protection of Prince Grigory Grigorievich Romodanovsky, who administered the border military districts and served as Muscovy's instrument in the Hetmanate. Romodanovsky directed Russian propaganda, bribed the Cossack elite, and promoted Moscow – loyal candidates for the hetmanship. Nevertheless, Barabash was eventually captured and executed when Muscovy tried to manipulate him for their objectives in controlling Ukraine²¹.

The death of Pushkar at Poltava, Barabash's execution after being intercepted from Muscovy, and the bloody suppression of the Poltava uprising facilitated efforts to strengthen cooperation with the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Hetman Vyhovsky therefore decided to conclude the Treaty of Hadiach with the Commonwealth.

The Hadiach Agreement arose from the discontent of the Hetmanate's social, economic, and political elite following the Pereiaslav Treaty. It was not the rank-and-file Cossacks or peasants, but only the elite who recognized the threat Muscovy posed to the nascent Hetmanate. This agreement was not a restoration of the Commonwealth's former territorial structure but an attempt to establish a joint Polish-Ukrainian state.

²⁰ R. KOWALCZYK, 'Polacy i Ukraińcy dwa bratanki...', s. 35.

²¹ *Hetmani zaporoscy w służbie króla...*, s. 226–244; R. KOWALCZYK, 'Sicz Zaporoska w drugiej połowie XVI stulecia...', s. 52–57; R. KOWALCZYK, 'Ukraina kraj na rozdrożu Europy. Czy Ukraina miała szansę na niezależny byt państwowy do wybuchu i wojny światowej', *Україна між Польщею та Росією*, вип. 1, К., 2016, с. 183–186; Р. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Україна до і після Кримської війни', *Наука Крим*, вип. 2, К., 2016, с. 61–67; R. KOWALCZYK, 'W cieniu walk, wojen i rewolucji. Trudna droga Ukrainy do wolności...', *Ukraina Magna*, vol. I, К., 2016, s. 171–173.

After 1654, Ukraine experienced significant turmoil. Khmelnytsky, by signing the Pereiaslav Agreement, had relied on Muscovy's support for the Cossacks against the Commonwealth, assuming it would be similar to his alliance with the Tatars at the outset of the 1648 uprising. He underestimated Muscovy's cunning and inadvertently became both the founder and the legacy – bearer of the independent Cossack state – the Hetmanate. Muscovy, fully aware of Ukraine's strategic importance in the struggle for primacy in the Black Sea region and ultimately in Central and Eastern Europe, began to impose its authority ruthlessly in Dnieper Ukraine. Bribery and the assassination of political opponents were commonplace. Gradually, Muscovy stripped the Cossacks of rights in their hard-won state, while marginalizing the legitimate Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the Kyiv Patriarchate to subordinate it under the Moscow Patriarchate.

The Hadiach Agreement, signed on 16 September 1658, restored, in a federal framework, the coexistence of Poles and Ukrainians within a single state. The Hadiach Union legally and internationally nullified the Pereiaslav Agreement. Moscow, misrepresenting its terms, continued propagandistically to claim that Ukraine had been subordinated to Muscovy. The Hadiach Union created three legally equal entities: the Crown, the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, and the Ruthenian Principalit²².

²² The Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the Constantinople Patriarchate was the continuation of the Orthodox Metropolis of Kyiv, established with the baptism of Kyivan Rus' in 988 by King Volodymyr I of Kyiv. The beginnings of Christianity in Ukraine, however, can be dated to 957, when Princess Olga was baptized in Constantinople. Kyivan Rus' received Christianity from Byzantium, which resulted in the Orthodox Metropolis of Kyiv being characterized by pomp, Oriental influences, richness of form, ritual, and sacred ornamentation. The Orthodox Metropolis of Kyiv lost its significance during the period of feudal fragmentation. Upon his death in 1054, Yaroslav the Wise divided Rus' among his sons. The principle of succession to the princely throne introduced by Yaroslav, based on seniority, did not prevent the disintegration of political unity. In the north arose the Novgorod Republic; in the northwest, the Principality of Polotsk; in the southwest, the Galician and Volhynian principalities. In the central lands the most important were the Principalities of Turov and Smolensk; in the northeast, the Rostov-Suzdal (Vladimir-Suzdal) and Ryazan principalities; and in the southeast,

The Treaty of Hadiach was Poland's response to the situation that emerged in Ukraine after the death of Bohdan Khmelnytsky. The

the Chernihiv and Pereiaslav principalities. Over time, this division deepened. Princes who managed to seize Kyiv were regarded as superior in the feudal hierarchy and bore the title of Grand Prince. Efforts to overcome fragmentation were made at the Congress of Liubech in 1097, convened by the then Grand Prince of Kyiv, Sviatopolk II Iziaslavych. Besides the grand prince, the congress included: Prince Volodymyr II Monomakh of Pereiaslav, Prince Davyd Sviatoslavich of Smolensk, Prince Oleg of Chernihiv, Prince Davyd Ihorevich of Volodymyr-Volyn, and Prince Vasylo Rostyslavych of Terebovlia. Volodymyr Monomakh, a talented ruler, temporarily restored the authority of the grand prince and halted the disintegration. Renowned as a vanquisher of the nomadic Polovtsians, Monomakh strengthened Rus' for a time. Yet after the death of his son Mstislav in 1132, centrifugal tendencies prevailed, ushering in full-scale feudal fragmentation. Each of the twelve principalities developed into an independent political-administrative center. Polotsk declared independence in 1132, followed by Novgorod in 1136. The princes of Kyiv lost control of Volhynia (1154), Pereiaslav (1157), and Turov (1162). Although Kyiv retained symbolic significance, it was repeatedly seized and plundered. The devastating raid by Prince Andrei Bogolyubsky of Rostov-Suzdal in 1169 stripped Kyiv of its former importance. After capturing Kyiv and assuming the title of Grand Prince, Andrei installed his own vassals in the city, beginning with his younger brother Gleb Yuryevich. From then on, the princes seated in Kyiv were vassals of more powerful rulers elsewhere. Andrei thus separated the senior princely title from Kyiv itself. Over time, princes of Vladimir-Suzdal, Galicia-Volhynia, Chernihiv, and Smolensk placed their own clients in Kyiv, while sometimes ruling directly. To distinguish vassals in Kyiv from genuine overlords, the title "Grand Prince of Kyiv or Vladimir and All Rus'" was introduced. By the early fourteenth century, rulers of Moscow, Tver, Suzdal, Nizhny Novgorod, Ryazan, Pronsk, Yaroslavl, and Perm also adopted grand princely titles. Around 1305, the title "Grand Prince of All Rus'" appeared, used exclusively by the princes of Vladimir, Tver, and Moscow.

Fratricidal struggles, excessive military pomp, and political disunity left Rus' vulnerable to external attack. The Mongol threat intensified in the early thirteenth century. After the crushing defeat of Rus'-Cuman forces at the Battle of the Kalka River in 1223, Batu Khan subjugated nearly all Rus' lands, sparing only Polotsk, Pinsk, and Novgorod, though even Novgorod was forced to pay tribute. In 1240, Batu seized Kyiv. The Mongols did not govern directly, but demanded the confirmation of princely candidates in Vladimir, who then held seniority over other princes. Under Yaroslav II Vsevolodovich, the Kyivan principality lost its remaining independence to Vladimir, as sanctioned by the Golden Horde. Princes of Kyiv henceforth were vassals of Vladimir and no longer resided in Kyiv. The destruction of Kyiv in 1240 also diminished the authority of the Orthodox Metropolitan of Kyiv. Its seat was moved first to Lviv, then in 1299 to Vladimir-on-Klyazma. Lithuania exploited the weakened state of Rus', conquering most western

Polish side sought to win over the Ukrainian elites – the Cossacks – by offering them the opportunity to realize their political aspira-

principalities between 1240 and 1392. Kyiv was defeated by Lithuanian forces on the Irpin River in 1320, becoming dependent and eventually incorporated directly into Lithuania in 1362. In 1325, the seat of the Metropolis of Kyiv was transferred to Moscow. The Rurikids of Moscow, taking advantage of Kyiv's decline and Lithuanian expansion, styled themselves rulers of the Grand Duchy of Moscow from 1263, and from 1305 assumed the title "Grand Prince of All Rus'", though illegitimately. Moscow sought to usurp the role of the Kyiv Metropolis as the pre-eminent Orthodox authority, despite the fact that Kyiv, as the ancient metropolis that had received Christianity from Byzantium, historically held that role. In 1448, the Moscow Metropolis unilaterally declared independence from Constantinople. A decade later, in 1458, the Kyiv Metropolis was formally divided into two: the Lithuanian-based Kyivan Metropolis and the Moscow Metropolis. After the fall of Constantinople in 1453, Moscow aspired to inherit Byzantium's legacy and the leadership of Orthodoxy. Favorable geopolitics aided this ambition: with the Balkans under Ottoman control, Moscow emerged as the only independent Orthodox polity. Moscow cultivated historical myths and propaganda, styling itself as Byzantium's heir. The theory of the "Third Rome" emerged, presenting Moscow as the legitimate successor to Rome and Constantinople. In 1472, Grand Prince Ivan III married Sophia Palaiologina, niece of the last Byzantine emperor, an alliance orchestrated by Pope Paul II. Moscow adopted the Byzantine double-headed eagle and ceremonial forms. In 1478, Ivan III became the first to use the title "Tsar of All Rus'". His successors launched a long-term policy aimed at unifying all Rus' under Moscow, legitimized by their claim to Byzantine inheritance. In 1547, Ivan IV "the Terrible" was crowned "Tsar of All Rus'", inaugurating the Tsardom of Russia. In 1589, the Moscow Metropolis, by means of falsifications, secured autocephaly from Constantinople, gaining patriarchal status. By the late sixteenth century, feudal fragmentation of Rus' had ended, with the last appanage principality abolished in 1591. As the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth declined, Moscow gradually subjugated Ukrainian Orthodox lands. A turning point came with the Treaty of Grzymułtowski in 1686, signed in Moscow. Through bribery in Constantinople, Muscovite envoys secured a tomos transferring the Kyiv Metropolis from the Patriarchate of Constantinople to Moscow. From then on, the Orthodox Church in Ukraine was subordinated to the Moscow Patriarchate, which became an arm of Muscovy's political power. Religion, harnessed to Moscow's patriarchate, served as an instrument of Russification of Ukrainian lands. The 1686 arrangement legitimized Moscow's interference in the confessional affairs of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. See: J. WOLIŃSKI, *Polska i kościół prawosławny*, Lwów, 1936, s. 112–116; J. HRYCAK, *Historia Ukrainy 1772–1999. Narodziny nowoczesnego narodu*, Lublin, 2000, s. 171–179; A. НИЖОВСКИЙ, *Самые знаменитые монастыри и храмы России*, Москва, 2000, с. 28–33; N. JAKOWENKO, *Druga strona lustra. Z historii wyobrażeń i idei na Ukrainie XVI–XVII wieku*, Warszawa, 2002, s. 86–94; A. MICHAŁEK, *Słowianie*

Khan of the Golden Horde, Tokhtamysh, at the gates of Moscow in 1382.
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tions within the framework of a common state, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. In this instance, however, the Poles showed little originality: they simply transformed the Cossacks into nobility. The Duchy of Rus' (the Ruthenian Principality), was to be created from the voivodships of Kyiv, Bratslav, and Chernihiv. Within the Duchy, separate offices were established, just as in the Crown and the Grand Duchy of Lithuania: the offices of hetman, marshal, chancellor, vice-chancellor, and treasurer of Rus'. Deputies from the Duchy of Rus' were to sit in the sejm (lower house of parliament), while Orthodox bishops were to enter the Senate.

The Duchy of Rus' was to have its own army, treasury, ministries, and offices, all under the direct authority of a hetman chosen by the Cossacks themselves. The nobility of all three states were to elect the king jointly and to send envoys to the General Sejm. In the Duchy of Rus', the higher Orthodox clergy were granted equality with the Latin clergy. They were given the right to sit in the Senate, with the provision that in the Kyiv voivodship senatorial offices were reserved exclusively for the Orthodox, while in Bratslav and Chernihiv they were to be divided equally between Catholics and Orthodox. One thousand members of the Cossack elite received ennoblement at once, while one hundred Cossacks from each regiment, confirmed by the hetman, were to receive noble status annually from the king. The treaty also provided for the inclusion of thirty thousand Cossacks in the regular registered army.

Thus, the Poles made Ukraine – renamed the Duchy of Rus' – a fully equal partner in the Commonwealth alongside the Crown and Lithuania, while also granting the Orthodox clergy equality with

wschodni, Warszawa, 2005, s. 72–78; L. ĆWIKŁA, *Polityka władz państwowych wobec Kościoła prawosławnego i ludności prawosławnej w Królestwie Polskim, Wielkim Księstwie Litewskim oraz Rzeczypospolitej Obojga Narodów w latach 1344–1795*, Lublin, 2006, s. 44–47; B. BUDZIAK, *Kryzys i reforma. Metropolia kijowska, patriarchat konstantynopolski i geneza unii brzeskiej*, Lublin, 2008, s. 67–78; L. PODCHORODECKI, *Tatarzy*, Warszawa, 2010, s. 59–68; D. DĄBROWSKI, *Król Rusi Daniel Romanowicz. O ruskiej rodzinie książęcej, społeczeństwie i kulturze w XIII w.*, Kraków, 2016, s. 92–99; P. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Давні військові українські та польські традиції: порівняльний аспект', *Народна творчість українців у просторі та часі. Науковий збірник*, Луцьк, 2018, с. 253–256.

their Latin counterparts. On 22 May 1659 the Polish Sejm ratified the Treaty of Hadiach. This represented a major breakthrough in relations with Ukraine and offered a chance for a common statehood and for resisting Russian expansion. The Poles thus granted Ukraine and the Cossacks what they had fought for since the early seventeenth century, after the death of Hetman Petro Konashevych-Sahaidachny. Yet the shift in relations came too late. The Commonwealth was already too weak, Russian influence in Ukraine too great, and the war that had lasted since 1648, with its river of blood, had drawn a deep line of division between Ukrainians and Poles²³.

The Muscovites were well aware of Ukraine's importance and did everything to ensure the treaty's failure. As a result of their countermeasures, the Hadiach Union was never fully implemented, and Bohdan Khmelnytsky's son Yurii – an obedient puppet – became hetman. He proved to be a perfect instrument for Moscow's policy in Ukraine, drawing his supporters to the Muscovite side. Moscow distributed gold, and some Cossack commanders threw their support behind Yurii Khmelnytsky²⁴. These were pro-Muscovite officers who opposed any agreement with the Commonwealth and resisted both the Hadiach Union and the authority of Hetman Ivan Vyhovsky. It should be noted that Moscow's success in winning over some of the Cossack elite was facilitated by the immense bloodshed since the outbreak of Khmelnytsky's uprising in 1648. These animosities could only have been overcome with time – but Moscow did not allow it. Fully aware that Ukraine and dominance in Eastern Europe were the stakes, the Muscovites made excellent use of the Commonwealth's weakness.

On 27 October 1659 the so-called Second Treaty of Pereiaslav was concluded. On one side it was signed by the puppet hetman of

²³ J. KACZMARCZYK, *Rzeczpospolita Trojga Narodów: mit czy rzeczywistość: uгода hadziacka – teoria i praktyka*, Kraków, 2007, s. 112–121; P. KROLL, *Od ugody hadziackiej do Cudnowa. Kozaczyzna między Rzeczpospolitą a Moskwą w latach 1658–1660*, Warszawa, 2008, s. 89–96.

²⁴ 'Jerzy (Jurij) Chmielnicki – hetman zaporoski (1640/1641 – po 1684)', [w:] *Hetmani zaporoscy w służbie króla i Rzeczypospolitej*, red. P. KROLL, M. NAGIELSKI i M. WAGNER, Zabrze 2010, s. 280–281.

the Zaporizhian Host, Yurii Khmelnytsky; on the other, by Prince Aleksei Trubetskoi on behalf of Tsar Aleksei. Trubetskoi, a former voivode of the Commonwealth who had betrayed Poland in 1654 to fight for Moscow, was a ruthless careerist who pursued his aims without scruple – even committing massacres of his own subjects, as after the capture of Mstsislaw on 22 July 1654.

The Second Treaty of Pereiaslav reduced the Zaporizhian hetman to a mere vassal of Moscow. The hetman lost all independence in foreign policy; the Zaporizhian Host was subordinated to Russia. At the tsar's command, the Cossacks had to march and fight alongside Muscovite forces, and the hetman was forbidden to undertake military action without the tsar's consent. In effect, the Cossacks were stripped of any independent political role. Free Ukraine was dead. What Hetman Petro Konashevych-Sahaidachny and Bohdan Khmelnytsky had fought for was trampled beneath Muscovite boots, and simultaneously betrayed by a group of Cossacks for Moscow's silver. Russian garrisons were introduced into Ukraine's key strongholds, to be maintained at the expense of the local population.

The treaty's articles revealed the complete subjugation of Ukraine to Moscow, eliminating Cossack autonomy. The hetman could no longer appoint or dismiss colonels without Moscow's approval, nor could the Cossacks elect a new hetman freely. Moscow also targeted the independent Kyiv Patriarchate: the Orthodox Metropolitan of Kyiv was forced to recognize the authority of the Moscow Patriarchate.

The Second Treaty of Pereiaslav marked the end of hopes for a free Ukraine, so arduously won by the Zaporizhian Cossacks and Khmelnytsky in their bitter struggle with Poland. The renewed Polish-Muscovite war was extremely bloody, showing how deeply entrenched Moscow's influence in Ukraine already was. After the Treaty of Hadiach, Moscow struck directly at Ukraine, attacking Hetman Vyhovsky's forces, which had sided with the Commonwealth. As always, the Muscovites found traitors who, for silver and promises of office, betrayed Vyhovsky. The Muscovite army of Prince Aleksei Nikitich Trubetskoi – who had deserted the Commonwealth for Russia – crossed the Dnipro and marched on Konotop, laying siege

to the fortress. They were joined by nearly 7,000 Cossacks loyal to the pro-Russian hetman Ivan Bezpaly. Konotop was defended by a Cossack garrison faithful to Vyhovsky. Determined to relieve the fortress, Hetman Vyhovsky marched to its aid, supported by Commonwealth troops and by the Crimean Tatars²⁵.

At Bakhchisarai the Hadiach Union and the creation of the Duchy of Rus' had not been received with enthusiasm, but the Tatars nevertheless maintained their alliance with Poland in order to help Warsaw bring an end to the Swedish-Polish war and to draw the Commonwealth's attention back to the eastern frontier – an outcome the Crimean Khanate desired.

As a result, the combined Cossack-Polish-Tatar army (16,000 Cossacks under Hetman Ivan Vyhovsky, 4,000 Poles under the command of the Kyiv stolnik Krzysztof Łasko, and nearly 30,000 Tatars under Khan Mehmed IV Giray himself) moved against the Muscovites. Upon learning of the relief force, the Russian commander Trubetskoy dispatched a cavalry detachment of about 9,000 men under the command of Semen Pozharsky, including 2,000 Cossacks loyal to Hetman Bezpaly, to confront Vyhovsky's troops. The Muscovites defended the crossing over the Sosnivka River. Vyhovsky divided his forces into two parts: the Poles and Cossacks tied down the Muscovite forces while simultaneously seizing and destroying the bridge, cutting off the Muscovites' retreat. Meanwhile, Mehmed IV Giray's horde outflanked the Muscovite positions, crossed the river, and struck Pozharsky's corps from the rear, from the left flank. It was a brilliant victory, though Hetman Vyhovsky would never have achieved it without the allies of the Poles at that moment – Mehmed IV Giray's Tatars. The Tatars then raided Muscovite territory, devastating the Sevsk and Belgorod regions. Reportedly, they destroyed 10,000 estates and carried off 27,000 captives²⁶.

Despite Vyhovsky's victory, the Muscovites did not relent. They exploited the rebellion of Martyn Pushkar for propaganda

²⁵ R. KOWALCZYK, 'Polacy i Ukraińcy dwa bratanki...', s. 35–36.

²⁶ А. Г. БУЛЬВИНСЬКИЙ, 'Конотопська битва 1659 р.', *Український історичний журнал*, 3 (1998): 76–83.

purposes and incited another uprising of Ukrainian peasants, the so-called the ‘czerń’ emphasizing social grievances – namely the poverty of ordinary peasants in contrast to the enrichment of the Cossack elite and senior officers, who had become a landed class akin to the Polonized Ukrainian nobility of the Commonwealth before 1648.

During this uprising, Yurii Nemyrych, co-founder of the Duchy of Rus’ was murdered. Nemyrych had been a fervent advocate of establishing the principality and sought a distinct status for Ukrainian lands within the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. At the very moment when it seemed his idea had materialized – when the Sejm ratified the Hadiach Agreement and he became Ruthenian Chancellor of the Principality – Muscovite intrigue reached him²⁷. After the deaths of Nemyrych and Hetman Vyhovsky, the idea of reviving the Duchy of Rus’ was never again pursued, either by the Commonwealth or by the Cossacks²⁸.

The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, however, was too weak, while Muscovite influence among parts of the Cossack elite was too strong, to expel Muscovy from Ukraine. Although the campaign of Chudniv in 1660 offered hope of driving the Russians out, in the end it became clear that the fate of Ukraine would remain contested. For although, on 17 October 1660, an agreement was concluded between the Commonwealth and the Cossacks, Ukraine’s future was still unresolved.

In the negotiations held during the battle of Chudniv, the Cossack Hetman Petro Doroshenko and Colonels Mykhailo Khanenko and Ivan Bohun took part. The Treaty of Slobodyshche restored the

²⁷ J. TAZBIR, ‘Polityczne meandry Jerzego Niemiryca’, *Przegląd Historyczny*, 75, 1 (1984): 37–38.

²⁸ K. KOSSARZECKI, *Kampania roku 1660 na Litwie*, Zabrze, 2005, s. 16–34; R. ROMAŃSKI, *Cudnów 1660*, Warszawa, 1996, s. 63–78; L. PODHORODECKI, *Zarys dziejów Ukrainy*, s. 101–109; L. PODHORODECKI, *Chanat krymski i jego stosunki z Polską w XV–XVIII wieku*, s. 287–316; *Hetmani zaporoscy w służbie króla...*, s. 256–287; J. KACZMARCZYK, *Rzeczpospolita Trojga Narodów: mit czy rzeczywistość: ugoda hadziacka – teoria i praktyka*, Kraków, 2007, s. 112–121; P. KROLL, *Op. cit.*, s. 89–96; R. KOWALCZYK, ‘Sicz Zaporoska w drugiej połowie XVI stulecia...’, c. 46–56.

provisions of the 1658 Hadiach Union but omitted the establishment of a Ruthenian Principality as a third constituent of the Commonwealth. The Zaporozhian Host renounced allegiance to the Tsar and pledged loyalty to the Polish king. The Cossacks were forbidden to seek foreign protection and ordered to join in joint military action against Moscow. The treaty annulled the so-called Second Pereiaslav Agreement but offered the Cossacks nothing in return. Thus, they failed to become a permanent component of the Commonwealth, as Nemyrych had envisioned. They never became part of the *nation of the chosen* – the noble estate of the Commonwealth. The fate of Ukraine was to be decided by force. The power that gained primacy in the Black Sea region would control Ukraine. Whether it would be Moscow, the Crimean Khanate, the Ottoman Empire, or the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth was determined in the final decades of the seventeenth century. One thing was certain: whoever secured Ukraine would dominate both Eastern and Central Europe.

King Jan II Casimir's Left-Bank Expedition of 1663–1664 extinguished the Commonwealth's last chance. The weak, anarchic state had no strength left. The Commonwealth had bled itself white in fratricidal conflicts and in defending the Polish nobility – manipulated by magnates – against the imagined absolutist designs of Jan Casimir, a threat fabricated by the opposition magnates themselves. The Lubomirski Rokosz and the defeat of royal forces at Czystochowa in 1665 epitomized the collapse of the state. The “noble nation” – the *chosen nation* of the Commonwealth – prevailed, bought by the money of Jerzy Sebastian Lubomirski and Poland's neighbors: Emperor Leopold I Habsburg, Elector Frederick William, and King Karl XI of Sweden, all eager to ensure that the Commonwealth remained a weak, powerless entity²⁹.

By the Truce of Andrusovo, signed on 30 January 1667, the Crown lost Chernihiv Voivodeship and much of Kyiv Voivodeship, i. e., the Left Bank. The Grand Duchy of Lithuania lost Smolensk Voivodeship, captured in 1611 and held after the Smolensk War

²⁹ W. KŁACZEWSKI, *Jerzy Sebastian Lubomirski*, Wrocław i in., 2002, s. 88–94; S. PŁAZA, *Rokosz Lubomirskiego*, Kraków, 1994, s. 1124–117.

(1632–1634). Kyiv was to remain in Russian hands for only two years, but the Muscovites never returned the Ukrainian capital. Ultimately, the weakened Commonwealth lost Left-Bank Ukraine under the Treaty of Moscow of 6 May 1686, known as the Grzymułtowski Peace, named after Poznań Voivode Krzysztof Grzymułtowski, who represented the Commonwealth. The treaty, proclaimed a *perpetual peace*, ended the Polish-Russian war that had begun in 1654 and sanctioned Russia's seizure not only of Left-Bank Ukraine with Kyiv but also of Smolensk, Sieveria, Chernihiv land, Dorohobuzh, and Starodub.

The chance for Poles and Cossacks to coexist in a single state – the Commonwealth – was irretrievably lost. Both Poles and Ukrainians, and especially the Cossack elite, were to blame. Their mutual animosities and lack of a vision for functioning within a common political organism were exploited by the Muscovites – enemies of both Poles and Ukrainians striving for dominance in this part of Europe. The absence of a timely agreement, a shared vision of coexistence, enabled the Russians to build a powerful empire, subordinating first the Ukrainians, then the Poles. The Muscovites achieved all their goals by exploiting Polish-Ukrainian antagonisms. Ukraine entered the period later known in historiography as the Ruina (“Ruin”), while Hetman Petro Doroshenko, seeing the Commonwealth weakening, sought an alliance with the Ottoman Empire. Yet Muscovy's position was too strong, and Doroshenko's efforts were thwarted both by Jan III Sobieski and by the Muscovites. As a result, in 1670 the Cossack hetmancy went not to Doroshenko but to Mykhailo Khanenko.

Although the great Turkish campaign against Muscovy in 1677–1678, when Ibrahim Shaitan with Tatar support and then Grand Vizier Kara Mustafa invaded Ukraine under Russian control, brought some success, Doroshenko was politically ruined. The 1678 expedition, despite its military achievements, failed to alter the situation. Fearing excessive Ottoman influence in the region and the prospect of Ukraine's direct incorporation into the empire, the Tatars entered negotiations with Moscow. The Muscovites reaped immense success: desperate to avoid confrontation with the Ottoman Empire,

then at the height of its renewed power, they emerged relatively unscathed. In 1681, the new Khan Murad Giray concluded an armistice with Moscow at Bakhchisarai. Preoccupied with the looming war against the Habsburgs, the Ottomans accepted the status quo.

Hetman Petro Doroshenko, by then politically bankrupt, was compelled to accept Muscovite protection, and Ukraine – the Hetmanate – fell into the period of the *Ruina*. The Great Northern War and Hetman Ivan Mazepa's alliance with King Karl XII of Sweden represented the last chance to preserve the Hetmanate's independence and check Muscovy's westward advance. The defeat at Poltava and the death in exile of Mazepa, the last free hetman, sealed Ukraine's fate: it became a Russian colony³⁰.

Moscow destroyed Ukraine's independence. After the signing of the Grzymułowski Peace, it gained freedom of action in Ukraine. The last independent hetman of Ukraine, Ivan Mazepa, although he attempted to resist Tsar Peter I's efforts to curtail the autonomy of the Hetmanate and ultimately abolish it, saw the final chance for independence lost with the defeat of Karl XII. Mazepa had begun negotiations with Stanisław Leszczyński and Karl XII. In 1708, he allied himself with Leszczyński, signing an agreement in his capital, Baturyn, with Karl XII as guarantor.

The Muscovites, aware that the stakes were supremacy in Europe, launched an effective propaganda campaign in Ukraine, portraying Mazepa as a traitor. At the same time, they undertook military action. The Muscovite forces under Prince Aleksandr Danilovich Menshikov, exploiting the betrayal of one of Mazepa's supporters, captured the Hetmanate's capital, Baturyn, and mercilessly massacred the Ukrainian population, including women and children. The Muscovites committed atrocities, raping women, girls, and children, before slaughtering them. As a reward for this massacre of thousands of innocent civilians – women, children, and the elderly – Ale-

³⁰ Д. ДОРОШЕНКО, *Гетьман Петро Дорошенко*, New York, 1985, с. 234–278; Н. КОСТОМАРОВ, *Мазепа*, Москва, 1995, с. 283–315, 398–409; Т. ТАЙРОВА-УАКОВЛЕВА, *Ivan Mazepa and the Russian Empire*, Montreal; London; Chicago, 2020, p. 345–374.

ksandr Menshikov received Baturyn in 1725 from Empress Catherine I Alekseyevna.

Despite attempts to restore independence after Mazepa's death on 2 October 1709, led by the new hetman Pylyp Orlyk, who placed Ukraine under the protection of Khan Devlet Giray II, these efforts failed. The expedition of Devlet Giray II's Tatars, Orlyk's Cossacks, Polish supporters of King Stanisław Leszczyński under the command of Kyiv voivode Józef Potocki (a staunch opponent of the Saxon dynasty on the Polish throne), and Ottoman forces into Ukraine had some chance of success. Yet it was undone by Russian silver. Even though Tsar Peter I's Muscovite army might have been destroyed on the Prut in 1711, Russian intrigue, the power of tsarist diplomacy, and the lure of gold prevailed. Bought with Muscovite bribes, the peace signed by Grand Vizier Baltacı Mehmed Pasha on 17 July 1711 allowed Russia to escape defeat. The last chance to change the balance of power in the Black Sea region was squandered. Ukraine, like the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, fell into Russian hands. The period of a free and autonomous Ukraine the Hetmanate – came to an end. Cossacks, Ukrainians, and Poles alike became victims of their own political immaturity and of Muscovite calculation, which skillfully exploited Polish-Ukrainian antagonisms and for centuries enabled Russia, and later the Soviet Union, to manipulate and subjugate nations.

After Hetman Mazepa's defeat and the death or emigration of much of the Cossack elite, the Russians gradually dismantled the Hetmanate's autonomy. Ultimately, the Hetmanate was abolished in 1764 by Empress Catherine II. Following its liquidation, she transformed it into the Little Russian Governorate (*guberniya*), in which the only surviving vestige of the Hetmanate was its territorial division into ten regimental districts. Yet Catherine II abolished this in 1781 as well, dividing its lands into the viceroyalties (*namestnichestva*) of Novhorod-Siverskyi, Chernihiv, and Kyiv. Only after her death did Paul I briefly restore the Little Russian Governorate, formed from these viceroyalties, with Chernihiv as its capital. After Paul's assassination, however, the governorate was again abolished.

In 1803, Tsar Alexander I divided its territory into two smaller governorates: Poltava and Chernihiv³¹.

The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, meanwhile, under Augustus II the Saxon, sank to the level of a passive object in international politics. The Russian victory at Poltava in 1709 and Peter I's salvation on the Prut in 1711 secured Muscovy's primacy in the Black Sea region. Following Sweden's final defeat and the signing of the Treaty of Nystad in 1721, Russia dominated not only the Baltic but all of Eastern and Central Europe. After 1709, the Commonwealth became a powerless state, dependent on Peter I, a dependency symbolized by the so-called Silent Sejm of 1717.

Augustus II attempted to strengthen royal power, but the magnate oligarchy, defending its own influence under the guise of protecting "Golden Liberty" against Saxon absolutism, opposed these reforms. The magnates and their noble clientele formed the Tarnogród Confederation (1715). The ensuing civil war was concluded by the Warsaw peace settlement and the Silent Sejm of 1717, which left the state's system unchanged. At that point, the Commonwealth became dependent not only on Russia but also, after Peter's death, on Berlin and Vienna. Foreign courts interfered freely in its internal affairs. On the eve of Augustus II's death, they concluded the Treaty of the Three Black Eagles, signed in Vienna on 13 September 1732 by Austria and Russia, later joined by Prussia. The pact violated the principle of free election and demonstrated that the Commonwealth had become a pawn in the hands of its neighbors.

Although the powers had agreed not to support either a Wettin candidate or Stanisław Leszczyński, French diplomatic activity on behalf of Leszczyński prompted Vienna and St. Petersburg to change

³¹ T. ТАЙРОВА-ЯКОВЛЕВА, *Op. cit.*, p. 367–388; Н. КОСТОМАРОВ, *Op. cit.*, с. 412–418; Р. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Україна до і після Кримської війни', с. 62–74; R. KOWALCZYK, 'Sicz Zaporoska w drugiej połowie XVI stulecia...', с. 56–59; R. KOWALCZYK, 'Ku wolności. Polska i Ukrainka droga do niezależnego bytu państwowego i wzajemna koegzystencja w okresie prymatu Rosji Carskiej', *Сверцина в історії України*, вип. 10, Глухів; К., 2017, s. 110–112; P. KROKOSZ, 'Od sprzedawcy pierożków do generalissimusa. Zawrotna kariera Aleksandra Mienszykowa', *Perspektywy Kultury*, 1(24) (2019): 146–149.

course. Fearing that Leszczyński's election might bring reform and the abolition of 'Golden Liberty' – the very basis of the Commonwealth's impotence, which made foreign interference so easy – the powers settled on Frederick Augustus II of the Wettin dynasty as their candidate. The future King Augustus III secured Austrian and Russian backing by renouncing claims to the Habsburg throne and to the duchy of Courland.

In the face of such international agreements, the Polish nobility's hostility toward the Saxons no longer mattered. At the convocation sejm, the nobility resolved that the king must be a Pole and a Catholic. Leszczyński was legally elected on 12 September 1733 by 12,000 nobles. He was supported by most senators, bishops, the primate, and the majority of magnate families, including the Czartoryskis, Załuskis, Potockis, Jabłonowskis, Rzewuskis, Mniszeks, and others. Yet 906 supporters of the Wettins, backed by Russian bayonets under General Peter Lacy, staged a rival election and offered the throne to Frederick Augustus II. Saxon-Russian armed intervention ensured that Augustus III, though never legally elected, ascended the Polish throne.

The masses of nobles backing Leszczyński formed the Dziaków Confederation, but they could not resist foreign armies. The military superiority of neighboring states was overwhelming. Broad noble support for Leszczyński was not the result of a realization of the need for reform and the abolition of 'Golden Liberty', but rather of resentment toward Saxon rule and opposition to foreign meddling in domestic affairs. Under the Saxons, foreign troops entered deep into the Commonwealth, occupying its territories, looting, plundering, and committing atrocities against the local population.

The decline of the Commonwealth accelerated. Most sejms were disrupted. Although part of the progressive nobility recognized the need for reform, and the demand for change grew, Poland ultimately disappeared from the map of Europe as a result of the three partitions of 1772, 1793, and 1795. The Commonwealth suffered the same fate as the Hetmanate in 1764 and the Crimean Khanate in 1783, when Russia annexed Crimea and destroyed the last Tatar nomadic state ruled by the Giray dynasty.

The failure to create a joint Polish-Ukrainian state – the Commonwealth of Three Nations – allowed Moscow to secure dominance in this part of Europe. After defeating Napoleon, Russia became the cornerstone of the new European order. The Congress of Vienna in 1815 established a continental peace system based on reactionary states committed to preserving the order. The Russian Empire was the pillar of this settlement, as reflected in the creation of the Holy Alliance (Russia, Prussia, Austria, France, and Great Britain), which, until the July Revolution, held continental Europe – and indeed much of the world – in check, intervening in Spain and blocking intervention in Peru³².

After the final liquidation of the Hetmanate in 1764, Ukraine was subjected to occupation. Until the collapse of Tsarist Russia in the First World War, Ukraine had no chance of regaining any form of independence.

In conclusion, why then did Moscow become the victor in the struggle for supremacy in the Black Sea region, and later in the Baltic Sea and in Central Europe? The Muscovite state gained dominance in the Black Sea region and primacy over the Hetmanate and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth because, in its struggle with Western states, it employed methods of lies, deceit, bribery, and betrayal, which derive from the Tatar-Mongol tradition of conducting war. This was the beginning of its domination over Eastern and Central Europe. Although Moscow gained dominance in the Baltic Sea region, pushing Sweden to the rank of a secondary state only after the peace treaty signed in Nystad on September 10, 1721, this is nevertheless closely connected with Ukraine, since the catastrophe for Ukraine and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, as well as the elimination of Sweden from the great power game, occurred at the Battle of Poltava in 1709 in Ukraine, on the territory of the Het-

³² D. KING, *Wiedeń 1814. Jak pogromcy Napoleona, bawiąc się, ustalali kształt Europy*, Poznań, 2009, s. 76–88; H. A. KISSINGER, *A World Restored. Europe After Napoleon: The Politics of Conservatism in a Revolutionary Age*, New York, 1964, p. 117–145; P. WANDYCZ, *Pax Europea. Dzieje systemów międzynarodowych w Europie 1815–1914*, Kraków, 2003, s. 63–74; W. ZAJEWSKI, ‘Aleksander I a rewolucja Hiszpańska 1820 roku’, *Przegląd Humanistyczny*, nr 1 (1976): 45–63.

manate. Karl XII, despite fighting for Sweden's position after the Battle of Poltava, was not able to change the situation. Therefore, for Moscow, gaining dominance in the Black Sea region was crucial because it allowed the Muscovite state to transform into an empire. The occupation of Ukraine – the Cossack state – the Hetmanate was the beginning of the creation of an empire based on conquests in the west. The next stage was the domination and seizure of most of the lands of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, and already after the defeat of Napoleon, the shifting of borders even further to the west through the takeover of the Duchy of Warsaw, under the changed name Kingdom of Poland, only slightly reduced in favor of the Kingdom of Prussia (the Grand Duchy of Poznań and Gdańsk).

This allowed Russia to transform into an empire dominating until 1914 throughout Europe, initially until the July Revolution of 1830, as the foundation of the new peace order created at the Congress of Vienna in 1815 by the victors over Napoleon (Russia, Prussia, Austria, Great Britain, and Bourbon France of Louis XVIII), the foundation of which was the Holy Alliance. However, after 1830, Moscow played a dominant role in Eastern and Central Europe. Despite the crushing defeat in the Crimean War and the necessity of giving up imperial ambitions toward the Ottoman Empire and the Balkans, it remained an empire until the outbreak of World War I, oppressing the subjugated nations of Central Europe – Poles, Ukrainians, Lithuanians, Finns, and the new nations awakening their national identity in the 19th century – Latvians, Estonians, and Belarusians. Without domination over Ukraine and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, that is, the acquisitions in the west, Moscow would not have transformed into an empire. It would have remained a closed, Asiatic state, as it was under Ivan IV the Terrible, whose ambitions of expansion to the west were challenged in victorious wars by the then still strong Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth.

The fundamental reason why Moscow turned out to be the victor in the struggle for domination in the Black Sea region, which proved crucial for domination over Eastern and Central Europe, were the institutional differences between the Muscovite state on

the one hand, and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the Hetmanate, and the Crimean Khanate on the other hand.

The Muscovite state was a strong centralized structure, where the role of the ruler, achieved at the expense of the elites – the aristocracy and the landowning boyar class – was dominant. The strongly centralized Muscovite state, with the overwhelming role of the ruling dynasty, the absolutism built over centuries, which in the case of Moscow can be called bloody despotism, allowed it to emerge from this struggle victorious. The Tsar, the ruler of the Muscovite state, was able, for the realization of his goals, to gather enormous resources in order, at the right moment, to strike militarily, to win, and to seize lands that territorially enlarged his Muscovite dominion, successively increasing Moscow's chance for domination.

It must be strongly emphasized that Moscow began its path to empire by exploiting the weakness of the nomadic states that arose after the collapse of the Golden Horde – the Kazan and Astrakhan khanates, but also the easternmost Siberian Khanate. Without the weakness of these nomadic states and the strategic mistakes of the Crimean Khanate, Moscow would not have taken over these vast lands. The Crimean Khanate, despite its power in the 16th century, remained a nomadic state, where *raison d'état* and the systemic nature of foreign policy, of strategic goals, clashed with the nomadic mentality of the Giray dynasty. As a result, the Crimean Khanate was not able to concentrate on a long-term program of destroying the foundations of the Muscovite state. Therefore, despite the enormous success of plundering and burning Moscow in 1572, it did not concentrate on eliminating the foundations of the Muscovite state, but in the following years focused on predatory raids on the southern frontiers of the Rurikid state. It was stated already at the beginning of the article that the reason lay not only in the nomadic character of the Crimean Khanate, in the very structure of the Giray state, in their nomadic perception of the *raison d'état* of the state. This was the systemic basis of the existence of the Crimean Khanate.

This allowed Moscow to rebuild its resources, and even to survive the period of the Time of Troubles, and the new dynasty –

the Romanovs – successively rebuilt its potential, waiting for the historical moment when Ukrainians and Poles sank into fratricidal struggles and then, after the reconstruction of the state by Peter I into an absolutist, bureaucratic Muscovite state, to subjugate the already then powerless Ukrainian and Polish states – the Hetmanate and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. The strength of Moscow lay in centralization and the increasingly strong construction of absolutism, which increased its power at the expense of the elites on which the Muscovite state had been based – the aristocracy and the boyars – up to its apogee in the times of Peter I, who eliminated any independence of the boyars and strictly subordinated the Russian elites, making them dependent on the Tsar from the ruling Moscow dynasty – the Romanov dynasty.

At the roots of the success of the Muscovite state lay the progressive weakness of the Jagiellonian state, and subsequently of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth and the newly formed Ukrainian state – the Hetmanate. In the case of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth and the Hetmanate, the institutional tendency was the opposite, as there was a lack of political centralization. In the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, the political system evolved towards elite absolutism. The ruling elite consisted of the oligarchy and the nobility. The ideology of the “chosen nation” derived from the nobility led to the oligarchization of the state. The noble nation, that is, the nobility in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, subordinated the other social estates, creating exploitative institutions and securing a source of income for the narrow noble elite at the expense of the other estates, which were deprived of political and economic rights. The nobility – the only estate in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth – possessed political rights and legal economic advantages over the burgher and peasant estates.

The winners were the oligarchy, which subordinated the nobility and, among the masses of the nobility, created a peculiar system of clientelism that allowed it to exert influence over the political system of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Consequently, the idea of the noble republic, as embodied in the Polish-Lithuanian

Commonwealth, was distorted by the oligarchy, and the nobility was demagogically indoctrinated. For the bewildered noble nation, the idea of noble freedom meant that the greatest threat was the growth of central – royal – authority. Royal absolutism became a slogan that united the nobility in blocking any attempts at reforms aimed at creating efficient state institutions, strengthening royal power, and building a regular army capable of defending the state's territory against hostile forces.

As a result of the establishment of exploitative institutions by the ruling elite – the oligarchy, which used the masses of the nobility – the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth remained an agrarian state trapped in the chains of secondary feudalism. The systemic weakness of the Commonwealth ultimately led to the collapse of the state. At the dawn of the 18th century, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth was a powerless state, the object of maneuvering by Peter I of Moscow and Karl XII of Sweden during the Third Northern War. Its internal condition was catastrophic, as the country was engulfed in civil war and fratricidal struggles among competing elective monarchs chosen through elections by feuding oligarchic factions – Stanisław Leszczyński, supported by the Swedes, and Augustus II – the Elector of Saxony, supported by Moscow.

The war in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth was extremely devastating and reflected the prevailing social conditions, the dominance of the oligarchy, the weakness of royal authority, and the collapse of institutions, especially central ones. In mid-1703, a confederation aimed against Augustus II, called the Greater Poland Confederation, was formed, reflecting the influence of Stanisław Leszczyński in this region of the Commonwealth. In February 1704, it transformed into the Warsaw General Confederation. On 12 July 1704, Stanisław Leszczyński was elected king. The election was confirmed by the electoral Sejm, but under Swedish protection in the Swedish military camp near Warsaw. The election was also ratified by the Bishop of Poznań, Mikołaj Świącicki, who had been abducted and imprisoned in Bautzen by Augustus II.

Opponents, however, at the initiative of Augustus II, established the Sandomierz Confederation, which mainly grouped sup-

porters from the Lesser Poland region. The marshal of the Sandomierz Confederation was Stanisław Ernest Denhoff, a typical representative of the contemporary magnate class, the oligarchic elite. The civil war between the supporters of the Sandomierz and Warsaw confederations lasted three years, until 1706. It caused massive destruction throughout the Commonwealth, which had become a powerless entity where conflicts were fought not only between the warring factions of the civil war – the Warsaw and Sandomierz confederates – but also by the armies of the opposing sides in the Third Northern War: the Swedish, Russian, and Saxon forces.

Although the civil war was won by Stanisław Leszczyński, the Battle of Poltava in 1709 altered the balance of power in the region and within the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. Stanisław Ernest Denhoff, unwilling to waste Moscow's victory at Poltava, invited the deposed Augustus, as chairman of the Warsaw General Council. Augustus was no longer a ruler following the Treaty of Altranstädt of 24 September 1706, in which he renounced the Polish crown. However, Denhoff's actions led to the restoration of Augustus II's rule in the Commonwealth. His influence in a country pacified by Russia increased significantly. Denhoff became so powerful that he began to independently negotiate with Saint Petersburg and Berlin. He was a typical representative of the elite, which in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth had become the ruling class and, due to the absence of strong central institutions and an efficient administration, contributed to the state's decline and eventual partitions³³.

The situation with the Hetmanate was more complex. Similar to the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, it suffered from a lack of political centralization. This resulted in interventions by stronger states – the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, Moscow, and the Ottoman Empire. Ultimately, Moscow emerged as the victor in the struggle for dominance in the Black Sea region. For Moscow, the occupation of Ukraine was a strategic, existential goal. Moscow's idea, without which building an empire would be impossible, was based on the false premise that the Muscovite state unites all Rus'

³³ See: E. CIEŚLAK, *Stanisław Leszczyński*, Wrocław i in., 1994, s. 283.

lands under its rule, hence the illegitimately adopted title of Tsar of All Rus'.

Ukraine was the heir of Kyivan Rus' of Volodymyr the Great. Kyiv was the capital of the Eastern Rite Church. For Moscow, the maintenance of an independent state with such a tradition – even if it was an egalitarian Cossack state, the Hetmanate, where the elites that created, or rather incorporated, exploitative institutions from the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth were a military elite derived from the Zaporozhian Cossacks, who in turn originated from runaway peasants – was unacceptable. For Moscow, the subordination and elimination of the Hetmanate represented the fulfillment of the promoted idea that the ruler of Moscow had the right to use the title Tsar of All Rus'. Moscow exploited the weakness of Kyivan Rus'.

In the 9th century, Rus' was governed from Kyiv, which was a very wealthy and radiant urban center. According to the chronicle *Tale of Bygone Years*, completed in Kyiv around 1113 by the monk Nestor (1056–1114), the territory of modern Ukraine was inhabited by East Slavic tribes, among whom the first proto-state formations emerged, known from Arab sources. In the mid-9th century, the local Slavs invited the Rus' (Scandinavian Vikings – Varangians) to govern and establish order in their lands. This is a widely accepted view among historians, corroborated by archaeological evidence, that the Norman leader Rurik founded a dynasty that lasted over 700 years.

The beginnings of Christianity in Ukraine can be dated to 957, and Kyivan Rus' officially adopted Christianity from Byzantium in 988 under King Volodymyr I the Great of Kyiv. Similar to Western Europe, where knighthood formed the core of military forces, in Rus' the warrior class constituted the foundation of the armed forces. They owned land and performed functions analogous to those of Western European knights. They were more dependent on the prince, although during the disintegration of Kyivan Rus' a system of vassalage and seniority developed. At that time, Kyivan Rus' was a powerful and wealthy state, but due to the adoption of Byzantine traditions, characterized by pomp, wealth, and splendor, it irreversibly lost the strong military tradition inherited from the West through the Varangians.

Upon his death in 1054, Yaroslav the Wise divided Rus' among his sons. He established the principle of succession to the princely throne according to seniority, but this did not prevent the political fragmentation of the country. Principalities such as Novgorod, Polotsk, Galicia, Volhynia, Turov, Smolensk, and Rostov-Suzdal, among others, emerged. In the central part of fragmented Rus', the most significant principalities were Turov and Smolensk; in the northeast, the Rostov-Suzdal principalities (Vladimir-Suzdal Rus') and Ryazan; and in the southeast, Chernihiv and Pereiaslav. Each of these principalities began to function as a separate political and administrative unit. Fratricidal struggles for dominance ensued, marking the beginning of the end of the great Kyivan Rus'.

The Kyivan ruler Volodymyr II Monomakh temporarily slowed the process of fragmentation, but could not halt it. Kyiv remained the symbol of supreme authority and a coveted prize for Rus' princes. However, the princes in Kyiv progressively lost control over Rus', for example, over Volhynia in 1154, Pereiaslav in 1157, and Turov in 1162. As a result, the city was repeatedly captured and plundered. Over time, rulers of principalities such as Moscow, Tver, Suzdal, Nizhny Novgorod, Ryazan, Pronsk, Yaroslavl, and Perm also began to assume the grand princely title, in addition to the Kyivan and Vladimir princes.

Following the defeat of the Rus'-Polovtsian forces at the Battle of the Kalka River in 1223, Batu Khan conquered all Rus' lands except for the principalities of Polotsk and Pinsk and the Novgorod Republic. Kyiv was captured in 1240. Although the inhabitants of Kyiv offered fierce resistance to the Mongols, they received no assistance from the Rus' principalities. Fragmented and conflict-ridden Rus' could not aid Kyiv. The Mongols carried out a massacre of Kyiv's population. Kyiv effectively ceased to exist, as confirmed by chroniclers' accounts and archaeological research³⁴.

Moscow exploited the weakness of fragmented Rus'. Moscow, which had little in common with the traditions of Kyivan Rus'

³⁴ Р. КОВАЛЬЧИК, 'Давні військові українські та польські традиції...', с. 251–260.

and the appanage principalities after the period of fragmentation, was instead rooted in traditions deriving from Mongol conquerors³⁵.

Moscow was fully aware that without patronage over the Kyivan metropolitanate, over the Church uniting the Rus' peoples, it could not achieve dominance over the souls of the Rus'. Conquering and absorbing the fragmented Rus' principalities was one matter; ruling over the spiritual and cultural life of the Rus' was another. The destruction of Kyiv by the Mongols in 1240 caused the Kyivan metropolitanate to be initially transferred to Lviv, and in 1299 to Vladimir-on-Klyazma.

The fragmentation of Rus' clearly weakened the Rus' principalities. The struggle of the Rus' against the Mongols was also exploited by Lithuania. After the Battle of Blue Waters in 1363, the Grand Duke of Lithuania, Olgierd Gediminas, incorporated Kyiv into the Grand Duchy of Lithuania, installing his son Vladimir there. The Lithuanian conquest of Kyiv marked a rupture in its previous ties with Northeastern Rus'. The Rurikid princes ruling the Muscovite principality took advantage of the Mongol destruction of Kyiv and the Lithuanian expansion into Rus', and in 1263 adopted the title of the Grand Principality of Moscow.

From 1305, they began using the title "Grand Prince of All Rus'", which was not rightfully theirs. This title was assumed by the Muscovite princes: Mikhail III of Tver, Ivan I Kalita, Simeon the Proud, and Vasily I Dmitrievich. In 1325, the seat of the Ky-

³⁵ М. Н. Покровский, 'Возникновение Московского государства и "великорусская народность"', [в:] М. Н. Покровский, *Историческая наука и борьба классов*, вып. 1, Москва; Ленинград, 1933; 'Русские', [в:] *Малая Советская Энциклопедия*, т. VII, гл. ред. Н. Л. Мещеряков, Москва, 1930, с. 506–509; 'Весь', [в:] *Большая Советская Энциклопедия*, т. IV, Москва, 1969–1978, с. 582–586; В. О. Ключевский, *Исторические портреты*, Москва, 1990, с. 41–42; С. М. Соловьев, *Чтения и рассказы по истории России*, Москва, 1989, с. 224–237; О. Царук, *Українська мова серед інших слов'янських: етнологічні та граматичні параметри*, Дніпропетровськ (Наука і освіта), 1998, с. 236; В. Антонович, 'Три національні типи народні', [в:] В. Антонович, *Вибрані історичні та публіцистичні твори*, К., 1995, с. 90–101; Р. Ковальчик, 'Кримський Ханат у боротьбі за володіння Золотої Орди. XV–XVI століття...', с. 87–91.

ivan metropolitanate was transferred to Moscow. However, Moscow's objective was to appropriate the role of the Orthodox Church from the Kyivan metropolitanate. In 1448, the Moscow metropolitanate unilaterally declared its independence from the Patriarchate of Constantinople. In 1458, the Kyivan metropolitanate was divided into two separate entities: the Lithuanian metropolitanate, seated in Kyiv, and the Moscow metropolitanate. From that time, Orthodox hierarchs in Moscow ceased to use the title of Metropolitan of Kyiv and All Rus'.

After the fall of the Byzantine Empire in 1453, the Muscovite state began aspiring to the role of Byzantium's heir and to serve as the head of the Orthodox Church. Moscow was aided in this endeavor by Pope Paul II, who believed that a union between the Catholic Church and the Moscow Orthodox Church was still possible. In 1469, he arranged the marriage of Sophia Paleolog, a member of the Byzantine Palaiologos dynasty, the youngest daughter of Thomas Palaiologos, despot of Morea, and Catherine Zaccaria, niece of Emperor Constantine XI Dragases, to Ivan III the Great of Moscow. The marriage of Ivan III and Sophia Paleolog took place in 1472 and facilitated Moscow's path to acquiring the role of supreme head of the Orthodox Church. Moscow adopted the Byzantine double-headed eagle as the state emblem and introduced Byzantine court ceremonial and symbolism from Constantinople.

In 1478, Ivan III the Great, as the first Muscovite ruler, assumed the title "Tsar of All Rus'." Beginning with Ivan III, the rulers of the former Grand Principality of Moscow promoted and pursued the unification of all Rus' under Moscow's rule, considering themselves heirs to Byzantine traditions. The symbolism employed by Moscow was highly significant and facilitated the achievement of this goal.

Another element of Moscow's intricate strategy was the coronation of Ivan IV the Terrible in 1547, when the designation "Tsar of All Rus'" was used for the first time in reference to the Grand Prince of Moscow. In 1589, the Moscow metropolitanate, using falsehoods and fabricated evidence, secured recognition of its auto-

cephaly from Constantinople, along with the establishment of a patriarchate. A pivotal moment occurred with the Treaty of Grzymultowski in 1686, signed in Moscow. At that time, Moscow's envoys bribed Mehmed IV in Constantinople to obtain a tomos from the Patriarch of Constantinople, subordinating the Kyivan Orthodox metropolitanate, previously part of the Constantinople patriarchate, to Moscow. The Orthodox Church in Ukraine was thus placed under the authority of the Moscow Patriarchate. The Moscow Patriarchate became an instrument of Moscow. From that point onward, religion-Orthodoxy subordinated to the Moscow Patriarchate – served the Russification of Ukrainian lands. Moscow sought to unify the Orthodox Church in Ukraine under the authority of the Moscow Patriarchate.

The 1686 agreement allowed Moscow to intervene in religious matters within the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, which included the right-bank part of Ukraine. The left-bank region – the Hetmanate – had already been dominated by Moscow earlier, following the failure of Hetman Petro Doroshenko's political program based on the Ottoman Empire. This was further facilitated by the reluctance of the Crimean Khanate, which feared an increase in Turkish power directly along its Ukrainian borders. Once again, despite military failure, Moscow achieved success by exploiting the divergence between the Crimean Khanate and Turkey.

The situation in the Black Sea region worsened with the transformation of the Muscovite state under Tsar Peter I. He sought to subordinate the Muscovite state firmly to the Romanov dynasty and to create a modern bureaucratic state modeled on Western practices. To achieve this, it was necessary to dismantle the existing governance structures within the Muscovite state. He curtailed the power of the Muscovite aristocracy – the boyars – by dissolving the Boyar Duma that had elected him tsar. Peter introduced the Table of Ranks, creating a completely new social hierarchy of privileged classes. All of Peter I's reforms concerned state governance, the redistribution of authority, and the restructuring of power among the elite. It must be emphasized that these reforms did not target the millions of feu-

dal peasants or the weak urban bourgeoisie and merchant class of Muscovy. The focus was exclusively on the elite – the aristocracy, the boyars – who, in Muscovy, constituted 1% of the population exploiting 99% through feudalism, which had taken its most extreme form there: a system of forced labor under strict control, a form of serfdom that was extremely exhausting and combined with cruelty³⁶.

Peasants were not only prohibited from moving freely, but their owners could sell them to other landowners; peasants were therefore sold or exchanged, for example, for horses. Men and women were separated from their families and resettled in the peripheries of the Muscovite state to colonize its frontier territories. Sexual assaults on innocent girls and severe floggings that could result in disability or death were commonplace. It is worth noting that the poverty of peasants was more extreme on estates owned by members of the dynastic family – the so-called appanage lands – than on private estates³⁷.

Peter I introduced the Table of Ranks, a system that established strict subordination to the tsar. He took control of the Moscow Patriarchate, turning the ecclesiastical hierarchy into his officials and making the Orthodox Church an instrument of state power. Peter thus stripped the existing aristocracy and church hierarchy of their authority, concentrating power in his own hands—that is, the Romanov dynasty. He also moved the capital from Moscow to Saint Petersburg³⁸. Saint Petersburg was built by peasants from Muscovy and Ukraine forced into brutal, backbreaking labor, with thousands perishing during its construction. The new capital of the Muscovite

³⁶ A. GERSCHENKRON, *Europe in the Russian Mirror*, New York, 1970, p. 38–47; J. BLUM, *Lord and Peasant in Russia*, New York, 1967, p. 236–287; G. T. ROBINSON, *Rural Russia under the Old Regime*, New York, 1963, p. 86–112.

³⁷ P. KROPOTKIN, *Wspomnienia rewolucjonisty*, tłum. M. SARNECKA, K. LATONIOWA, wstęp. W. ŚLIWOWSKA, Warszawa, 1959, s. 83.

³⁸ A. GERSCHENKRON, *Europe in the Russian Mirror*, p. 38–47; A. GERSCHENKRON, *Economic Backwardness in Historical Perspective*, Harvard, 1962, p. 163–189; J. BLUM, *Op. cit.*, p. 236–287; M. E. FALKUS, *The Industrialization of Russia 1700–1914*, London, 1972, s. 34–58; G. T. ROBINSON, *Op. cit.*, p. 86–112; M. DOBB, *Studia o rozwoju kapitalizmu*, tłum. H. HAGEMEJER, J. ZDANOWSKI, Warszawa, 1964, s. 27–63.

Capture of Azov after the second siege, which took place from
 June 7 to July 29, 1696. The war between Moscow and
 the Ottoman Empire was part of the Holy League War.
After the unsuccessful siege of 1795, Moscow invested in foreign commanders:
 Franz Yakovlevich Lefort, a mercenary born in Geneva,
 became the commander of the fleet, and Patrick Leopold Gordon, a Scot,
 became the commander of the Muscovite troops.
The capture of Azov was a success for Moscow and a step toward
 dominance in the Black Sea region. After taking Azov,
Moscow stationed a permanent garrison of 500 Muscovite soldiers
in the fortress and relocated 3,000 families from Ukraine to Azov.
Public domain

state was, therefore, literally built on the bones of Ukrainians and Muscovites.

Peter I transformed the foundation of the armed forces by creating a new-order army with instructors from the West³⁹. Consequently, he did not hesitate to brutally suppress the Streltsy uprising in 1689 – the former tsarist guard and backbone of Muscovy’s military – as well as later uprisings such as those of the Bashkirs or the Don Cossack ataman Kondraty Bulavin⁴⁰. All these measures served the strict subordination of the Muscovite state to the tsar’s authority.

Peter I prioritized the development of an economy linked to the arms industry, which was to form the foundation of Romanov rule. Consequently, throughout the entire 18th century, Russia’s largest industrial sectors remained the mining and metallurgical industries of the Urals, as well as centers in Karelia in the northwestern part of European Russia and in Siberia. In coastal trading centers, shipbuilding industries developed, producing sailcloth and ship fittings, such as in Saint Petersburg and Arkhangelsk. In Moscow, the cotton industry – Muscovite cotton manufactories – belonged to the nobility, who compelled serfs to work in these establishments. These enterprises were therefore inefficient in terms of labor productivity, yet they constituted the foundation of autocratic rule – the Romanov dynasty. The construction of arms industries, mines, and metallurgical centers relied on Western specialists. Without them, Peter I would not have transformed Muscovy into an absolutist, bureaucratic state with a strong army and a rigid feudal system⁴¹.

With such a centralized structure equipped with a strong new-order army built with Moscow’s resources and expertise, the

³⁹ A. GERSCHENKRON, *Europe in the Russian Mirror*, p. 38–47; J. BLUM, *Op. cit.*, p. 236–287; G. T. ROBINSON, *Op. cit.*, p. 86–112.

⁴⁰ Z. WÓJCIK, *Dzieje Rosji 1533–1801*, Warszawa, 1971, s. 231–234; T. KORZON, *Historia nowożytna: Od 1649 do 1788 roku*, Warszawa, 1903, s. 339–341; *Mała Encyklopedia Wojskowa*, Warszawa, 1967, s. 198.

⁴¹ I. BLANCHARD, *Russia age of silver: Precious-metal production and economic growth in the eighteenth century*, London, 1989, p. 102–137; И. А. ЗАЙЧКИН, И. Н. ПОЧКАЕВ, *Русская история*, Москва (Издательство “Мысль”), 1992, с. 446–449; П. П. фон Винклер, *Из истории монетного дела в России*, Москва, 2005, с. 14–32.

Map of the Battle of Stănilești – the decisive battle fought from July 20 to 22, 1711, during the Prut Campaign. Public domain

Hetmanate stood no chance. Its only hope was chance. Chance often determines the fate of nations and states. Such a situation arose during the period of the Third Northern War. Hetman Ivan Mazepa decided to seize this unique opportunity for the free Cossack state – the Hetmanate.

However, Karl XII's campaign against Moscow ended in defeat at Poltava. It must be acknowledged that Karl XII's plan had been well-prepared and appeared promising. The plan assumed that while the main Swedish army, commanded by Karl himself, marched on Moscow to force Peter into a decisive battle, General Georg Lybecker would advance from Finland into Ingria, General Adam von Lewenhaupt would move south from Courland to join Karl XII, and General Ernst von Krassow, together with Stanisław Leszczyński, would march into Ukraine after defeating the Sandomierz confederate forces. Karl XII had thus arranged support from nearly all directions⁴².

However, a combination of circumstances, a severe winter, and the scorched-earth policy implemented by Moscow's troops under Peter I's orders led to the defeat of the Swedish forces. The effectiveness of the Muscovite troops in Ukraine also played a decisive role. The Muscovites captured the Hetmanate capital, Baturyn, mercilessly killing the Cossacks and the entire population of the city, including women and children. This was facilitated by the betrayal of the Cossack colonel of the Pryluky regiment, Ivan Nos, who allowed Alexander Menshikov's Muscovite forces to enter. The absence of these battle-hardened Cossacks at Poltava significantly contributed to the Swedish defeat⁴³.

Karl XII lost approximately 10,000 soldiers at Poltava. However, an even greater disaster was the surrender of General Adam von Lewenhaupt, whose army still numbered over 16,000 soldiers. At Perevolochna, he capitulated to Menshikov, who com-

⁴² F. G. BENGTTSSON, *The life of Charles XII king of Sweden 1697–1718*, London, 1960, p. 270–274.

⁴³ С. ПАВЛЕНКО, *Доба гетьмана Івана Мазепи в документах*, К., 2008, с. 712–718.

manded only about 9,000 troops. Lewenhaupt should have faced a firing squad for not even attempting to resist⁴⁴.

Ukraine fell into Muscovite hands for over 200 years. The Hetmanate was abolished in 1764. Russia pursued a deliberate policy of assimilation, Russifying Ukrainians and attempting to erase the memory of Kyivan Rus' and the Hetmanate. It employed well-known methods of propaganda, falsehood, and violence. All Ukrainian artists, scholars, scientists, and officers born in Ukraine were treated as Russians. Ukrainians had no choice: to pursue higher education, they had to study at Russian institutions. This policy extended to Ukrainian painters, as vividly illustrated in the article *Ukrainian Painting of the 19th and 20th Centuries: Outline of Main Trends* by Professor Svitlana Kravchenko⁴⁵.

The consequence of the Battle of Poltava was the subjugation of Ukraine and the lands of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, establishing Russian dominance in Eastern and Central Europe. By acquiring Ukrainian, Polish, Crimean, and Baltic territories, Peter I transformed Moscow into an empire that dominated this part of Europe until 1914. Despite the fall of Imperial Russia in 1918, Russia – having embarked on a path of imperial dominance at the beginning of the 18th century – remained on that path up to the present day, despite the change of state name from Imperial Russia to the Soviet Union, and later, following the collapse of the Soviet system, to the Russian Federation. The beginning of this geopolitical shift was Russia's attainment of primacy in the Black Sea region.

Рафал Віктор КОВАЛЬЧИК

Чому Москва виграла змагання за домінування у Чорноморському регіоні? Причини та наслідки

На середину XVIII ст. на східних кордонах Європи виникла нова потуга – Російська імперія, що надалі значною мірою визначала

⁴⁴ F. G. BENGTSOON, *Op. cit.*, p. 360–389.

⁴⁵ S. KRAVCHEKNO, 'Українське мalarство XIX і XX wieku: zarys głównych nurtów', *Techne. Seria Nowa*, Nr 3 (2019): 29–49.

політику не лише в регіоні, а й у цілій Європі. Яким чином вдалося відсталій, другорядній державі посунути на маргінез міжнародної політики такі потуги, як Річ Посполита та Кримський ханат, чому саме Москва виграла змагання за спадщину Золотою орди й аналізує автор у статті.

Саме Кримський ханат, як легітимний спадкоємець Золотої Орди, мав усі шанси залишатись гегемоном у регіоні Східної Європи та Чорного моря зокрема. Однак Бахчисарай хибно оцінив зовнішні загрози. Лише час дав зрозуміти, що для Гераїв більшу небезпеку становила не Річ Посполита, а Московська держава. Річ Посполита, як і Гетьманщина були співмірними державами, з якими можна було досягати угод. Натомість Москва, попри всю відсталість, володіла непомірно більшими людськими та територіальними ресурсами. Ханат допустився помилки не знищивши Москву на початку XVI ст., коли мав таку можливість. Надалі Москва зростала, Кримський ханат слабшав. Врешті, на кінець XVIII ст. останній зійшов з політичної мапи Європи, а Москва, у формі Російської централізованої й деспотичної імперії перетворилася на значну мілітарну потугу та загрозу для сусідніх держав у євро-азійському регіоні, якою вона залишається до сьогодні. Першим суттєвим успіхом Москви на цьому шляху стало здобуття панівного становища в Чорноморському регіоні, завдяки перемогам над Кримським ханатом та Україною.

Ключові слова: Москва, Річ Посполита, Гетьманщина, Кримський ханат, геополітика.

Рафал Віктор Ковальчик, доктор історії, професор Лодзького університету (Лодзь, Польща),

Rafal Wiktor Kowalczyk, DS in History, professor of the University of Lodz (Lodz, Poland),

ORCID: 0000-0002-1071-6147